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Design Principles and Multifunctionality in Cell Encapsulation Systems for Tissue Regeneration

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Abstract

Cell encapsulation systems are being increasingly applied as multifunctional strategies to regenerate tissues. Lessons afforded with encapsulation systems aiming to treat endocrine diseases seemed to be highly valuable for the Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine (TERM) systems of today, in which tissue regeneration and biomaterial integration are key components. Innumerable multifunctional systems for cell compartmentalization are being proposed to meet the specific needs required in the TERM field. We review the variable geometries proposed to produce cell encapsulation strategies towards tissue regeneration, including spherical and fiber-shaped systems, and other complex shapes and arrangements that better mimic the highly hierarchical organization of native tissues. The application of such principles in the TERM field brought new possibilities for the development of highly complex systems, which holds tremendous promise for tissue regeneration. The complex systems aim to recreate adequate environmental signals found in native tissue (in particular during the regenerative process) to control the cellular outcome, and conferring multifunctional properties, namely the incorporation of bioactive molecules and the ability to create smart and adaptive systems in response to different stimuli. We also discuss the new multifunctional properties of such systems that are being employed to fulfill the requirements of the TERM field.

Keywords: bioactive molecules, capsules, cell encapsulation, fibers, hierarchical systems, hydrogels, spheres, stem cells, stimuli-responsive systems, tissue regeneration

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1. Introduction: From immunoisolation to multifunctional devices

Protection was the main purpose of the pioneer cell encapsulation systems. Cells should maintain their normal physiological activity and release biomolecules while being protected from the interaction of the immune system by the presence of a barrier. This “immunoprivileged feature” was achieved for the first time in 1933 using an amniotic membrane tissue.^[1] After implantation in the abdominal cavity of pigs, a prolonged cell survival of encapsulated tumor

cells could be observed. However, the therapeutic potential of the technology was not recognized in that time. Later, in 1954, the concept of “diffusion chamber” to graft therapeutic cells was introduced,^[2] while also emphasizing for the first time the importance of biocompatible polymers on the composition of cell encapsulation matrixes. Another major development for the field was the development of an “artificial cell”, by the release of hemolysate isolated from erythrocytes from microcapsules (1-100 μm diameter) in 1964.^[3] It was the first time that functional bioactive molecules were released from exclusively engineered materials, i.e. in the absence of living organisms. The era of bioartificial organs had just started among the scientific community, and in 1975 is proposed the first artificial endocrine pancreas.^[4] Beta cells were isolated from neonatal rats and then cultured on bundles of artificial capillaries (Amicon XM-50 fibers). Remarkably, beta cells were responsive to changes in glucose, and insulin was being released in similar levels compared to standard culture flasks used as control. The overarching principle of cell encapsulation was then to provide a long-lasting solution for treating secretory cell dysfunction.^[5-7] The successful immuno-masked presence of transplanted cells was a remarkably achievement for organ transplantation by avoiding the use of immunosuppressant drugs and their associated side effects. The immunoprotection feature also allowed the use of allo- and xenogenic cells, solving cell-sourcing issues and challenges. Another remarkably milestone on the history of cell encapsulation systems is the pioneering work of Lim and Sun with poly(L-lysine) (PLL) coated alginate beads as islets encapsulation systems.^[8] Since then, the scientific community has been challenged to design multifunctional immunoisolation devices that combine an adequate diffusion of essential molecules for cell survival, as well as the exchange of bioactive molecules.

Knowing the background of cell encapsulation systems it is understandable that the majority of works reported in the literature are related with the applicability of the technology to treat a wide range of endocrine diseases, including anemia,^[9] dwarfism,^[10] hemophilia B,^[11] kidney^[12] and liver^[13] failure, pituitary gland^[14] and central nervous system^[15] disorders, and, its major application field, diabetes mellitus.^[8] In fact, the immunoprotective research line is dominated by the encapsulation of pancreatic islets. This is driven by the high number of diabetic patients and the recognized benefits of cell encapsulation strategies.^[16] In parallel, with the discovery of new polymers and biomaterials, cell encapsulation strategies became more complex, and its use was extrapolated to respond to requirements of other biomedical fields, such as in the Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine (TERM) field. In TERM field, the concept of encapsulating cells is different from the immunoprotection required to treat endocrine diseases. In TERM applications, it is often desirable that the encapsulation matrix degrades while the encapsulated cells proliferate and create their own extracellular matrix (ECM) to ultimately integrate the new tissue. Different pro-healing components, such as growth factors and cytokines can be co-encapsulated with cells while being released in a sustained fashion through the encapsulation matrix. Moreover, various encapsulation systems can be implanted through minimally invasive procedures by injection, allowing the compartmentalization of cells and other desirable cargo within complex geometries.

The majority of cell encapsulation systems proposed for TERM are hydrogels, mainly due to a number of appealing features. Hydrogels provide a highly hydrated environment resembling the ECM of soft tissues, while maximizing molecules diffusion. They can be easily functionalized to enhance cell-material interactions.^[17-20] Additionally, following implantation, the soft and flexible features of the hydrogel reduce the frictional or mechanical irritation of surrounding tissues. Some authors also claim that due to its hydrophilic properties, there is no interfacial tension with surrounding tissues and fluids, which minimizes cell adhesion and protein adsorption, resulting in high biocompatibility.^[21]

In the present review, we intend to highlight the emergence of sophisticated, “smart” and multifunctional-engineered cell encapsulation systems that in common aim to successfully stimulate the regeneration of damaged tissues, while describing their relevant design criteria and the processing methods. In particular, a special focus will be given on the use of hydrogels. The new cell encapsulations systems are discussed in terms of its variable three-dimensional (3D) structures, comprising spherical, fiber-shaped, and structures with increased 3D complexity, including multiscale devices obtained either from top-down or bottom-up approaches. Additionally, new features added to enhance the new multifunctional cell encapsulation systems are discussed, in which all of them have in common the same impetus: to improve viability and function of the encapsulated cells directing their activity in promoting the formation of new tissue.

2. Engineering cell encapsulation systems with variable geometries

One of the main drawbacks of using hydrogels in cell encapsulation strategies is their shape manipulation. Consequently, due to the ease of process, the most widely used hydrogel geometry for cell encapsulation systems is spheres. Over the years, with the development of new technologies to process hydrogels, new shaped systems are increasingly being developed, including fibers-shaped systems. Additionally, more complex structures, mainly resulting from the assembly of variable shaped building blocks by bottom-up approaches are being developed. In the present section, different examples of cell encapsulation systems with spherical and fiber-shaped geometries will be discussed.

Besides the geometry, other parameters of biomaterials are important, such as the surface properties (e.g., topography, charge, and wettability), size, porosity, and release of ions, since they dictate not only the diffusion efficiency but also the actuation of the immune system, and thus their biocompatibility/biotolerability. This relevant immune-related topic will not be addressed in the present review, but we advise the reading elsewhere.^[22-27]

2.1 Spherical systems

Cell encapsulation strategies with spherical shape are the most widely use. From a mass-transport perspective, spherical systems are able to provide an optimal surface-to-volume ratio for the diffusion of essential molecules for cell survival.^[28] In particular, microencapsulation strategies allow implantation through minimal invasive procedures by injection. In terms of conformation, spherical cell encapsulation strategies can be divided in (i) beads, the most studied and simple spherical system, and (ii) capsules. The difference between the two nomenclatures is that capsules comprise the presence of a membrane surrounding the core environment. Cell matrixes without a surrounding membrane but encapsulating other materials besides living cells are also called capsules. Therefore, the terminology of capsules is variable in TERM. In the present review, the capsules terminology refers to all the systems surrounded by a membrane. In order to increase the complexity of beads in cell encapsulation systems, those systems have been combined with the incorporation of other materials, such as smaller beads^[29] or solid microparticles,^[30] as discussed in section 2.3 *Multifaceted and complex structures*. Most of the capsules are derived from beads, which are used as templates to produce the membrane. Capsules can be further divided into subcategories depending on the core state, namely (i) matrix-core/shell, (ii) liquid-core/shell, and (iii) cells-core/shell capsules (or conformal coating).

Matrix-core/shell capsules encapsulate cells within a jellified hydrogel matrix surrounded by a membrane. The most well-known system is the alginate capsules produced by ionotropic gelation of droplets containing cells after immersion in a bath of divalent ions, such as calcium or barium. Afterwards, the obtained beads are coated to produce the membrane by immersion in an oppositely charged polyelectrolyte such as PLL as first proposed by Lim and Sun.^[8] On the other hand, liquid-core/shell capsules encapsulate cells within a liquid matrix surrounded by a membrane. Using again the alginate capsules as an example, the system can be obtained by changing the localization of cells or other to be encapsulated materials in the solutions used in matrix-core/shell capsules, i.e. by dropping a cell suspension containing divalent ions into an alginate bath.^[31,32] Immediately a hydrogel membrane of alginate is formed surrounding the liquified core containing cells. An alternative methodology to obtain extremely thin membranes in the order of nanometers is to combine cell encapsulation techniques with the layer-by-layer (LbL) methodology. Using this technology, we proposed the co-encapsulation of cells and solid microparticles within a liquefied environment.^[33-37] Many refinements of the different techniques to produce spherical cell encapsulation systems have been attempted over the years, giving raise to the emerging of new production methods and new coating techniques, produced combining principles of microfluidics technology, superhydrophobic surfaces, and 3D bioprinting of hydrogels. The cells-core/shell (or conformal coating) is a more recently technique compared with the referred two types of subcategories of capsules, and comprises the direct coating of a cell mass using LbL technique.

Examples of beads and capsules as spherical systems used for cell encapsulation strategies in TERM applications are illustrated in **Figure 1**. **Table 1** summarizes the biomaterial, production technique, type of encapsulated cells, and the TERM application of examples of cell encapsulation systems with spherical structure.

Figure 1 - Different types of beads and capsules as spherical cell encapsulation systems. **(B1)** Alginate microbeads encapsulating human umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells. Scale bar is 200 μm . Adapted with permission.^[38] Copyright 2011, Elsevier Ltd. **(B2a)** Multicolored DEX-MA microbeads encapsulated within alginate beads. Scale bar is 1 mm. **(B2b)** Higher magnification of B2a. Scale bar is 200 μm . Adapted with permission.^[29] Copyright 2015, John Wiley and Sons. **(MS1)** Matrix-core/shell capsule encapsulating at the inner core living cells (green fluorescence), and dead cells at the outer layer (red fluorescence). Adapted with permission.^[39] Copyright 2014, Springer Nature. **(MS2a)** Bilayered DEX-MA matrix-core/shell capsule. Scale bar is 500 μm . **(MS2b)** Localization of encapsulated cells in the outer layer of the DEM-MA matrix-core/shell capsule (cells nuclei: blue-DAPI; F-actin filaments: red-phalloidin). Scale bar is 200 μm . Adapted with permission.^[40] Copyright 2013, John Wiley and Sons. **(LS1)** Liquid-core/shell capsule. Cells are encapsulated within the liquified alginate core, which is surrounded by a layer-by-layer chitosan-alginate membrane. Scale bar is 500 μm . Adapted with permission.^[41] Copyright 2011, John Wiley and Sons. **(LS2a)** Liquid-core/shell capsule co-encapsulating cells and solid surface functionalized microparticles. The liquefied core is surrounded by a multilayered membrane. Scale bar is 500 μm . **(LS2b)** Higher magnification of LS2a. Scale bar is 100 μm . Adapted with permission.^[34] Copyright 2013, American Chemical Society. **(CS1)** Coated cells. Scale bar is 4 μm . Adapted with permission.^[42] Copyright 2010, Royal Society of Chemistry. **(CS2)** Cell-core/shell capsule and the resultant coating-free daughter cell. Adapted with permission.^[43] Copyright 2002, American Chemical Society.

Table 1 – Examples of spherical cell encapsulation systems for Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine (TERM). The examples cover the type of biomaterial used to produce the different cell encapsulation systems, the production technique, the type of encapsulated cells, and the TERM application.

Abbreviations: hCSCs – Human Cardiac stem cells; rMSCs – Rat mesenchymal stem cells; hMSCs – Human mesenchymal stem cells; IMR-90 – Human fetal lung fibroblasts; hCSP – Human progenitor stem cells from the subchondral bone marrow; hPCs – Human placental microvascular pericytes; EDTA – Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid; HUVECs – Human umbilical vein endothelial cells; hUCMSCs – Human umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells; RGD – arginine-glycine-aspartic acid peptide sequence; TOBC – 2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl radical oxidized bacterial cellulose; PLL – Poly(L-lysine); ES – Murine embryonic stem cells; hASCs – Human adipose-derived stem cells; hAMECs – Human adipose-derived microvascular endothelial cells; MNPs – Magnetic nanoparticles; CHO-K1 – Chinese hamster ovary cells.

SHERICAL SYSTEMS	BIOMATERIAL	PRODUCTION TECHNIQUE	ENCAPSULATED CELLS	TERM APPLICATION	REF.
BEADS	Agarose with fibronectin or fibrinogen	Thermal gelation	hCSCs	Cardiovascular	[44]
	Agarose, collagen I, fibrin and dextran-sulfate	Water/oil emulsion	rMSCs or hMSCs and IMR-90	Cardiovascular	[45]
	Alginate	Calcium gelation	hCSP	Cartilage	[46]

	Alginate	Calcium gelation	hPCs	Vascular	[47]	
	Alginate	Calcium gelation with disodium EDTA	D1 MSCs	General	[48]	
	Alginate (macrobeads) Dextran-methacrylate (microbeads)	Calcium gelation (macrobeads) Photocrosslinking (microbeads)	L929	General	[29]	
	Alginate and fibronectin	Calcium gelation	rMSCs	Bone	[49]	
	Alginate and keratine	Calcium gelation	HUVECs	Vascular	[50]	
	Chitosan	Sodium tripolyphosphate gelation	L929	General	[51]	
	Collagen I	Thermal gelation	hMSCs	Bone	[52]	
	Collagen I	Thermal gelation	hMSCs	Cartilage	[53]	
	Oxidized alginate and fibrin	Calcium gelation	hUCMSCs	Bone	[38]	
	RGD-alginate	Calcium gelation	hMSCs	Bone	[54]	
	TOBC-alginate	Calcium gelation with nitrogen	NIH/3T3	General	[55]	
CAPS III FS	Matrix-core/shell	Alginate (core) PLL (shell)	Calcium gelation (core) Polyelectrolyte complexation (shell)	ES	Neural	[56]
		Alginate and collagen I (core) Collagen I (shell)	Calcium gelation (core) Polyelectrolyte complexation (shell)	hASCs	Adipose	[57]
		Dextran-methacrylate (core) Alginate (shell)	Photocrosslinking (core) Calcium gelation (shell)	L929	General	[40]
	Liquid-core/shell	Alginate (core) Chitosan and alginate (shell)	Calcium gelation followed by EDTA decrosslinking (core) Layer-by-layer (shell)	Saos-2	General	[41]
		Alginate (core) Chitosan and alginate (shell)	Calcium gelation followed by EDTA decrosslinking (core) Layer-by-layer (shell)	L929	General	[33]
		Alginate (core) Chitosan, alginate and PLL (shell)	Calcium gelation followed by EDTA decrosslinking (core) Layer-by-layer (shell)	L929	General	[34]
		Alginate (core) Chitosan, alginate and PLL (shell)	Calcium gelation followed by EDTA decrosslinking (core) Layer-by-layer (shell)	hASCs and hAMECs	Bone	[35]
		Alginate (core) Chitosan, alginate, PLL and MNPs (shell)	Calcium gelation followed by EDTA decrosslinking (core) Layer-by-layer (shell)	hASCs	Cartilage	[36]
		Dextran (core) Tetronic (T1107) derivatives (shell)	Pluronic F127	CHO-K1	General	[58]

2.2 Fiber-shaped systems

Fibers are long, thin and flexible structures that facilitate high-order assemblies such as nanoscale materials^[59,60] and textiles.^[61] In contrast with spherical cell encapsulation systems, fiber-shaped systems were not popularly employed until more recently. This is because the conventional mass-produced fibers require process parameters such as, high shear, melt temperatures, harsh chemical solvents, and high voltages^[62] which are incompatible with the required mild conditions for cell encapsulation systems. Nonetheless, fiber-based systems are an ideal platform for mimicking biological materials and tissue structures. Consequently, current research has begun to exploit fiber matrices for biomedical applications.^[62-64] Fiber-shaped systems can easily create 3D complex and hierarchical constructs *in vitro* mimicking the interconnected networks of native tissues, such as the tubular network of the cardiovascular systems, neural pathways, and the musculoskeletal system.^[65,66] The processing of fibers for cell encapsulation systems requires aqueous conditions with precisely controlled temperature and pH. The processing limitations coupled with the TERM biomimetic solutions led to the increasing production of fibers by microfluidics technique. In comparison to standard technologies, microfluidics offers a combination of improved properties for biomaterials

fabrication, including, reproducibility (low coefficient of variance), purity, yield, and it also allows mild conditions.^[62] Various fiber-shaped cell encapsulations systems have been proposed to encapsulate different cell types by microfluidic spinning technique.^[64,67-76] Microfibers are continuously formed in a microchannel with a coaxial flow composed by the fiber precursor solution and sheathed by the crosslinking agent. The fiber is produced inside the microchannel or after ejection after a physical or chemical crosslinking occurs. This method is similar to the wet spinning technique,^[77] but instead of a crosslinking bath, the crosslinking agent is supplied directly by the coaxial flow. A great advantage for cell encapsulation strategies is the fact that this technique does not require high voltages or temperatures. The diameter of the fibers can be easily tuned by adjusting the flow rate.^[64] Similar to spheres, the most common biomaterial used to produce fibers is alginate,^[18,69,70,73-75] but other polymers have been also employed, such as chemically modified gelatin,^[68,78] chitosan,^[79] collagen,^[80] and supramolecular hydrogels.^[76] Additionally, different types of cells have been encapsulated alone or in co-culture. Matrix-core fibers were proposed to encapsulate hepatocytes or fibroblasts using spinning microfluidics combined with a digital fluid controller.^[69] With this technique different parameters of the production of fiber could be controlled by switching the flow. In principle, the technique allows to fabricate spatiotemporally coded fibers with diverse chemical compositions, structures, gas bubbles, live cells, and morphologies. To demonstrate the spatial regulated control, fibers encapsulating hepatocytes and fibroblasts in multiple parallel layers were produced. The main aim was to propose a methodology able to produce fibers highly complex, thus mimicking the diversity of native tissues.

Overall, the production methods to produce fibers by microfluidics remain similar between the different strategies with only slight modifications of the technique, such as by exploring different laminar flows. A fiber-shaped cell encapsulation system was proposed using a double-coaxial laminar flow microfluidic device.^[71] The double-coaxial laminar flow allowed creating a microfiber-shaped inner core of ECM proteins, namely collagen type I and fibrin, which require longer gelation time compared to polymers, covered by a thin and tubular outer layer of mechanically stable and rapidly gelating alginate hydrogel. The alginate shell prevented the ECM proteins in the liquified core from diffusing out the core, until finally the structure is solidified into a hydrogel. Different cell types were encapsulated, namely fibroblasts, myocytes, endothelial, nerve or epithelial cells. Ultimately, the alginate shell is removed, resulting in a fiber-shaped cell encapsulation system only composed by cells and ECM proteins.

Besides matrix-core fibers, the simplest and commonly used system, fiber-shaped cell encapsulation systems can present other geometries. Depending on the core state and the presence of a membrane, fibers can be divided into (i) matrix-core fibers, (ii) hollow-core fibers, (iii) matrix-core/shell fibers, and (iv) liquid-core/shell fibers. In particular, hollow-core and liquid-core/shell fibers have been poorly described in the literature. In the case of hollow-core fibers, the majority of reports are related with the encapsulation of therapeutic cells within the lumen, which are then sealed with adhesive at both ends.^[81-84] This strategy is mainly employed to produce immunoisolation membranes, thus is not within the scope of the present review. In tissue regeneration, since the immunoisolation feature is not compulsory, hollow-core fibers are widely used as tubular structures usually to mimic the vascular network.^[61] Consequently, few studies have employed hollow-core fibers encapsulating cells within its matrix for TERM, although its production has been increased with the emerging of new techniques to produce cell encapsulation systems.^[70,78,85,86] Hollow fibers encapsulating cells within its matrix were first reported with alginate fibers encapsulating endothelial cells (HIVE-78) using a three-layer coaxial flow.^[70] Calcium chloride solution was used as the core and out-layer fluids to crosslink the alginate solution localized in the middle layer. The fabricated hollow fibers were then embedded into agar-gelatin-fibronectin hydrogels encapsulating smooth muscle cells (HIVS-125). However, this method lacked control over the lumen diameter of the microfiber. In fact, the lack of reports might be resultant from the difficulty to avoid the collapse of the lumen or, especially in the case of hydrogels, its obstruction after swelling. To control the lumen diameter of hollow microfibers, a coaxial triple cylinder was suggested.^[86] Aqueous solutions of dextran (core cylinder), alginate (intermediate cylinder) and calcium chloride (outer cylinder) were simultaneously extruded. The lumen diameter was controlled by the ratio of flow volume of dextran solution to total flow volume of dextran and alginate solutions (core volume ratio). Additionally, the outer diameter of the fiber could also be controlled. Currently, since hollow-fibers are challenge to obtain, cell encapsulation tubular structures for TERM applications are mainly obtained by wrapping a tubular structure with matrix-core fibers using complex microfluidics technologies, such as combined with weaving machines^[71] or multilayered

structures.^[87]

Liquid-core/shell fibers are barely reported in the literature.^[72,74,88] Alginate fibers encapsulating human kidney 293 cells transfected with GFP and coated with PLL were proposed.^[74] The alginate core was then liquified by sodium citrate treatment. Cells remained viable within the liquified core and cells formed a cylindrical multicellular aggregate after two weeks of culture. Others, used alginate fibers to encapsulate L929 cells, which were then coated with multilayers of alginate and chitosan using a LbL perfusion technique.^[88] The core was then liquified by EDTA treatment. The multilayered shell allowed to retain the cells within the liquefied core, as well as to assemble the liquid-fibers into a higher-order structure.

The recent methods to produce fiber-shaped systems allow a fine control of the diameter, composition, and radial organization. However, the surface of the produced fibers is usually smooth, and lacks the micro- and nano-features of natural tissues which guide and regulate cell behavior. In an attempt to recreate such conditions, fibers with microstructured surfaces have been successfully proposed encapsulating murine C2C12 myoblast cells and human osteoblasts encapsulation.^[89] Examples of different fiber-shaped systems used for cell encapsulation strategies in TERM applications are illustrated in **Figure 2**.

Table 2 summarizes the biomaterial, production technique, type of encapsulated cells, and the TERM application of examples of cell encapsulation systems with fiber-shaped structure.

Figure 2. Different types of fiber-shaped cell encapsulation systems. **(M)** Gelatin–hydroxyphenylpropionic acid (Gtn–HPA) matrix-core fibers encapsulating Madin-Darby canine kidney (MDCK) cells. Fibers were produced through the oxidative coupling of HPA moiety catalyzed by hydrogen peroxidase (H_2O_2) and horseradish peroxidase (HRP), and extruded by a multiphase lamina flow with a triple-orifice. The fiber was extruded by an inner hydrogel precursor (Gtn-HPA + HRP + MDCK cells) flow rate of $7.5\mu L \cdot min^{-1}$, a middle H_2O_2 rate of $17.5\mu L \cdot min^{-1}$ and an outer PBS flow rate of $75\mu L \cdot min^{-1}$. The cell suspension was added to and uniformly mixed with the Gtn-HPA+HRP solution prior to the loading of this precursor solution into the syringe pump. **(Ma)** Single layered cell-seeded Gtn-HPA fiber with MDCK cells labeled in green with PKH2 Green Fluorescent Cell Linker Kit. **(Mb)** cryosectional DAPI staining of Gtn-HPA fibers. Scale bar is **(Ma)** $400\mu m$ and **(Mb)** $50\mu m$. Adapted with permission.^[78] Copyright 2009, Elsevier Ltd. **(MSa)** Matrix-core/shell fiber encapsulating mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) in the core and bioactive glass nanoparticles (BGN) in the shell. BGN released silicon and calcium ions, which guided the differentiation of MSCs towards the osteogenic lineage. Phalloidin (green) and DAPI (blue) staining after 21 days of MSCs encapsulation in fibers with osteogenic differentiation medium and **(MSb)** without or **(MSc)** with BGN. Scale bar is $100\mu m$. Adapted with permission.^[80] Copyright 2015, Acta Materialia Inc. **(LS1)** Liquid-core/shell fibers encapsulating transfected cells with GFP in the liquid alginate core surrounded by a poly(L-lysine) (PLL) shell. The encapsulated cells were monitored immediately after production (day 0), and after 7 (day 7) and 14 days (day 14) post-encapsulation. Green fluorescence images of living human kidney 293 cells transfected with GFP were overlaid on bright-field images to visualize the fiber system. Scale bar is $400\mu m$. Adapted

with permission.^[74] Copyright 2008, Royal Society of Chemistry. **(LS2a-c)** Optical images of mouse embryonic stem (ES) cells encapsulated in liquified alginate (ALG)/PLL fibers after 5 days of *in vitro* culture. The liquid environment of the core of the fibers promoted the cellular self-assembly formation of compact cellular structures. The authors could assess that the morphology of the self-assemble tissue architecture depended on the diameter of fibers. **(LS2a and b)** When the fiber diameter was below 100 μm , ES elongated along the ALG/PLL liquid-core fibers and formed a long cylindrical cell colony. **(LS2c)** When the fiber diameter was about 180 μm , irregular cellular clusters formed and filled out the entire space of the ALG/PLL fibers). Scale bar is 200 μm . Adapted with permission.^[72] Copyright 2011, Elsevier Ltd. **(H1)** Confocal image of alginate hollow fibers encapsulating HIVE-78 cells (red) and embedded in agar-gelatin-fibronectin matrix encapsulating HIVS-175 cells (green) to emulate a tissue with networked microvessels. Fibers were produced by microfluidics using three fluids, which were introduced simultaneously via three separate inlets: a core fluid (crosslinking agent calcium chloride), a sample fluid (sodium alginate, 2% w/v, and HIVE-78 cells), and a sheath fluid (crosslinking agent calcium chloride). First, the coaxial flow (core and sample fluids) is generated and the gelation process starts at the interface between the core and the sample flow that forms along the inner wall of the hollow fiber. Then, sheath flow is introduced and results in the formation of three-layered coaxial flow. Fibers were then embedded into the AGF-hydrogel with HIVS-125 cells. Adapted with permission.^[70] Copyright 2009, John Wiley and Sons. **(H2a)** Hollow-core alginate fibers produced using a coaxial triple cylinder. For the production of fibers, aqueous solutions of dextran (core), sodium alginate (sample) and the crosslinking agent calcium chloride (sheath) were extruded simultaneously from the inner, intermediate and outer cylinders, respectively. Two types of mammalian cells could be separately located in the hollow core and the gel part of the fibers: red cells were encapsulated within the matrix of the fibers, while a suspension of green cells was added to the hollow region. **(H2b)** Fibers were pressed and, consequently, the green cells located at the hollow core were released. This evidenced the successful physical separation of cells. Scale bar is 500 μm . Adapted with permission.^[66] Copyright 2009, Elsevier B.V.

Table 2 - Examples of fiber-shaped cell encapsulation systems for Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine (TERM). The examples cover the type of biomaterial used to produce the different cell encapsulation systems, the production technique, the type of encapsulated cells, and the TERM application.

Abbreviations: HepG2 – Human hepatocellular carcinoma cells; Gtn-HPA – Gelatin-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid; HRP – Horseradish peroxidase enzyme; H_2O_2 – Hydrogen peroxide; MDCK – Madin-Darby canine kidney cells; PEG-DA – Poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate; hMSCs – Human mesenchymal stem cells; Alg-Ph – Alginate with Ph moieties; hPTCs – Human proximal tube cells; PGA – Propylene glycol alginate; PLL – Poly(L-lysine); BGn – Bioactive glass nanoparticles; rMSCs – Rat mesenchymal stem cells; hME – Human microvascular endothelial cells; EDTA – Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid; ES – Embryonic stem cells.

FIBER-SHAPED SYSTEMS	BIOMATERIAL	PRODUCTION TECHNIQUE	ENCAPSULATED CELLS	TERM APPLICATION	REF.	
Matrix-core	Alginate	Calcium gelation	L929	General	[73]	
	Alginate and chitosan	Polyelectrolyte complexation	Primary rat hepatocytes and L929	General	[69]	
	Alginate and chitosan	Calcium gelation	HepG2	General	[79]	
	Gtn-HPA	HRP and H_2O_2 crosslinking	MDCK	General	[78]	
	PEG-DA	Photocrosslinking	NIH/3T3	Vascular	[87]	
	Peptide amphiphile solution	Ionic (calcium) self-assembly	hMSCs or HL-1	Cardiovascular, neural and nerve	[76]	
Hollow-core	Alginate	Calcium gelation	HIVE-78	Vascular	[70]	
	Alginate	Calcium gelation	L929	General	[86]	
	Alg-Ph	HRP and H_2O_2 crosslinking	HeLa	General	[85]	
	Gtn-HPA	HRP crosslinking	MDCK	General	[78]	
	Gtn-HPA (inner layer) Polysulfone (outer layer)	HRP and H_2O_2 crosslinking	hPTCs	General	[68]	
	Alginate and PGA (core) Alginate and PLL (shell)	Calcium gelation (core) Polyelectrolyte complexation (shell)	NIH/3T3, HeLa or PC12	Hepatic, vascular, and musculoskeletal	[75]	
Matrix-core/shell	Collagen I (core) Alginate and BGn (shell)	Calcium gelation	rMSCs	Bone	[80]	
	Collagen I (pepsin- or acid-solubilized) or fibrinogen (core) Alginate (shell)	Thermal gelation (collagen I-core fibers) or ionic crosslinking with thrombin and calcium chloride (fibrinogen-core fibers)	Fibroblasts (NIH/3T3), myocytes (C2C12 or rat primary), endothelial cells (HUVECs or MS1), nerve cells (rat primary cortical cells or mouse primary neural stem cells) or epithelial cells (HepG2, MIN6m9 or HeLa)	Vascular, musculoskeletal or neural	[71]	
	Gtn-HPA (core and shell)	HRP and H_2O_2 crosslinking	MDCK	General	[68]	
	Gtn-HPA (core and shell)	HRP and H_2O_2 crosslinking	MDCK and hME	General	[78]	
	Liquid-core/shell	Alginate (core) Alginate and PLL (shell)	Calcium gelation followed by sodium citrate decrosslinking (core)	Human kidney 293 cells	Vascular	[74]

	Layer-by-layer (shell)			
Alginate (core) Alginate and chitosan (shell)	Calcium gelation followed by EDTA decrosslinking (core) Layer-by-layer (shell)	L929	General	[88]
Alginate (core) PLL (shell)	Ca ²⁺ gelation followed by sodium citrate decrosslinking (core) Polyelectrolyte complexation (shell)	Mouse ES	General	[72]

2.3 Multifaceted and complex structures

Native tissues are hierarchical assemblies of heterogeneous types of cells and ECM across multiple length scales. Inspired by that, different cell encapsulation strategies with complex structures have been increasingly proposed. Examples of multifaceted and complex systems used for cell encapsulation strategies in TERM applications are illustrated in **Figure 3**.

A commonly used strategy is the assembly of hydrogels as building blocks by bottom-up approach (**Figure 3. I-IV**). Bottom-up approaches have the potential to construct tissues with defined properties including spatial and temporal control at cellular level.^[90] An example of spherical building blocks composed by alginate beads encapsulating L929 cells and assembled by perfusion-based LbL technology was proposed.^[91] Due to the spherical shape of the beads, molds with variable shapes could be easily filled, and thus cell encapsulation systems with distinct final 3D macrostructures were obtained. After the construction of the membrane, the core was liquified by EDTA treatment. The system maintained its structural integrity, showing the feasibility of using LbL to assemble hydrogel building blocks. Other interesting bottom-up approaches to construct 3D structures of hydrogels are being explored using other assembly techniques. For example, the self-assembly of hydrogels with different geometries was demonstrated by placing microcubes of methacrylated gelatin (gelMA) into the surface of a higher density hydrophobic liquid (carbon tetrachloride or perfluorodecalin).^[92] Due to surface tension, complex hydrogel aggregates were observed. A second crosslinking step by UV light radiation was employed to consolidate the complex 3D structure. The hydrogel blocks were proposed to encapsulate different cell types, which could then be combined in one single structure to design multi-cellular structures. Precise control over the assembly process can be achieved by functionalization of the surface of the hydrogels in a more complex strategy. For that, cube-shaped hydrogels functionalized with single-stranded DNA segments were proposed as a molecular recognition-assisted self-assembly strategy.^[93] Results showed that hydrogels loaded with long complementary DNA strains could preferentially bind to each other and create complex microarchitectures. Others, produced multifaceted hydrogels co-encapsulating NIH 3T3 cells and magnetic nanoparticles, which conferred magnetic-response ability to the hydrogels.^[94] By spatially controlling the magnetic field, different biomimetic geometries could be (dome: diaphragm; sphere: islets; tube: vascular network; and hexagon: pancreas lobules). The different assembly methods of hydrogels encapsulating cells in order to fabricate complex structures by bottom-up approaches were elsewhere reviewed in detail.^[95]

A different approach is to use micromolding to fabricate complex templated hydrogels on a massive scale (**Figure 3. V and VI**). Generally, the molds can be made from different materials, such as metal and plastics, through soft photolithography and rapid prototyping.^[64] Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) elastomers are also widely used to fabricate the molding replica due to their tunable mechanical strength, optical transparency, and cytocompatibility.^[96] The process involves filling the molds with a pre-polymer solution that is usually photopolymerized, originating hydrogels with multifaceted shapes. Micromolding was combined with photopatterning techniques to spatially organize 3D hybrid hydrogel arrays based on gelMA and PEG derivatives. Mouse embryoid bodies (EBs) were encapsulated within the engineered constructs to study their interactions with different hydrogel compositions.^[97] For that, EBs were first seeded into the microwells on a PDMS substrate, followed by the sequential loadings of the two pre-polymer solutions and UV crosslinking through a photomask. The EBs were found to preferentially sprout into the gelMA hydrogel part, and thus led to induced polarity in the embryonic development, suggesting possible approaches to regulate the behavior of the stem cell niches for TERM applications.

A more automated strategy to construct cell encapsulation strategies with complex shapes are those fabricated using hydrogel rapid prototyping (**Figure 3. VII-X**). The main advantages are its speed and versatility, although with some strategies cell damage might occur. Therefore, the technique is limited in terms of fabrication processes, and also the range of biomaterials

than can be employed. Of relevance, the methodology allows to construct anatomically complex cell encapsulation systems, such as vascular networks.^[98,99] The 3D printing of vascular networks is a highly scalable platform that allows fabricating engineered tissue constructs in which vasculature and multiple cell types are precisely placed within the hydrogel matrix. This methodology allows increasing the diffusion of essential molecules by creating an extending network within the 3D structure of the engineered hydrogel, avoiding cell necrosis, one of the main issues in cell encapsulation systems. Other example of an anatomically complex cell encapsulation system using hydrogel rapid prototyping was the production aortic valves using hydrogels composed by natural polymers, such as alginate/gelatin hydrogels^[100] or combined with synthetic polymers, such as alginate with PEG diacrylate (PEG-DA).^[101] One of the main disadvantages of having complex 3D structures by hydrogels rapid prototyping is the lack of mechanical resistance. In order to solve this problem, an interpenetrating network of ionically crosslinked alginate and covalently crosslinked PEG was proposed to fabricate a hydrogel possessing high fracture toughness, while allowing the encapsulation of human mesenchymal stem cells.^[102] The unique tough and robust properties of the proposed hydrogel relied on the combination of two mechanisms, namely the reversible calcium crosslinking of alginate that dissipates energy under deformation, and the covalent crosslinked long-chain PEG that maintains high elasticity of the hydrogel. The capability of printing PEG-alginate hydrogels into various complicated 3D structures, including hollow cubes, hemispheres, pyramids, twisted bundles, and physiologically relevant shapes, such as human noses and ears, was tested. To produce complex shapes, the viscosity of the prepolymer solution was increased by including a nanoclay within the hydrogel. Human embryonic kidney (HEK) cells were encapsulated into a collagen type I solution, which then gelled throughout the interconnected pores of the printed PEG-alginate-nanoclay mesh to form a composite hydrogel. The encapsulated HEK cells remained viable up to 7 days of *in vitro* culture. The printed hydrogel structures were also highly deformable and tough, demonstrating that the nanoclay did not significantly affect the superior mechanical quality of the hydrogel.

Figure 3. Examples of multifaceted and complex systems used for cell encapsulation strategies in Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine applications. **(I)** Liquefied capsules by a perfusion-based layer-by-layer technique. Adapted with permission.^[91] Copyright 2014, Royal Society of Chemistry. **(II)** Production of hydrogels by liquified air-interface-directed self-assembly technique. **(II.a)** Photomask covering a PEG-cell suspension. **(II.b)** Photopolymerization by UV-light, and **(II.c)** cell-laden PEG microgels are obtained. **(II.d)** Floating microgels randomly distributed in hydrophobic solutions. Then, **(II.e)** microgels self-assemble and **(II.f)** UV-light is again applied, leading to the formation of bottom-up constructs. Scale bar is 2 cm. Adapted with permission.^[109] Copyright 2010, John Wiley & Sons. **(III)** Self-assembly of hydrogel cubes with uniform giant DNA glue modification. Two types of cube were produced: a red-cube with giant DNA-a and a blue-cube with giant DNA-a*, both cubes displaying the DNA sequence on two opposite faces. **(III.a)** 48-

nt sequences were uniformly amplified on the surface of red and blue cubes, leading to their assembly by hybridization between the complementary DNA sequences. **(III.b)** After mild rotation, assembled hydrogel cubes were imaged by microscopy. **(III.c and d)** Phase contrast and fluorescent microscopy images, in which hydrogel cubes were modified with **(III.c)** short 56-nt or **(III.d)** amplified giant DNA strands. Hydrogel cubes carrying complementary DNA-a were labeled in red and DNA-a* in blue with fluorescent microbeads, and stained with SYBR Gold. **(III.e)** Red and blue hydrogel cubes carrying complementary short (left) or giant (right) DNA strands failed (left) or succeeded (right) to assemble into aggregates, in the presence of non-modified yellow hydrogel cubes. **(III.f)** Red and blue aggregated cubes (left image) are then immersed in DNase treatment and consequently disassemble (right image). Scale bar is 500 μm in c, d, e and f. **(III.g–j)** Assembled red and blue hydrogel cubes with various edge lengths, namely **(III.g)** 30mm, **(III.h)** 200 mm, **(III.i)** 500 mm and **(III.j)** 1 mm. Giant DNA glue was uniformly amplified on the hydrogel surface. Scale bar is 1 mm and 50 mm in the inset of **(III.g)**. Adapted with permission.^[93] Copyright 2013, Springer Nature. **(IV)** Magnetic directed assembly of microgels produced by micromolding. Three-layered spheroids are obtained through the application of external magnetic fields. Scale bar is 500 μm . Adapted with permission.^[94] Copyright 2011, John Wiley & Sons. **(V)** Cell encapsulation in 3D gel objects with multiple shapes, namely crosses, squares, and cylinders. **(V.a)** Posts are obtained by photolithography of SU-8 photoresist on a silicon wafer. **(V.b)** Spin-casting PDMS around the produced posts generates a membrane with an array of variable holes in terms of shape and dimensions. **(V.c)** The obtained holes penetrate the PDMS membrane. **(V.d)** The produced PDMS membrane is immersed in a collagen cell suspension. **(V.e)** The filled PDMS membrane is incubated to allow the gelation of collagen. **(V.f)** Afterwards, the membrane is immersed in cell culture medium and the hydrogels are consequently released. **(V.g)** The obtained hydrogels are able to maintain the pre-defined shape. **(V.h–k)** Different shapes that can be produced with the PDMS membrane: **(V.h)** cross, **(V.i)** square cross-section encapsulating a single cell and **(V.j)** a side view of square cross-section module, and **(V.k)** cylindrical. Scale bar is 800 μm in **(V.h, j and k)** and 200 μm in **(V.i)**. Adapted with permission.^[104] Copyright 2008, McGuigan *et al.* **(VI)** Polarity induction in individual embryoid bodies (EBs) encapsulated in gelMA/PEG microgels with spatially patterned vasculogenic differentiation. **(VI.a and c)** Phase contrast images of EBs within microgels. **(VI. b and d)** DAPI-stained EB within PEG microgel with green microbeads and gelMA microgel with streptavidin-rhodamine (red). Scale bar is 600 μm in **(VI.a)** and 300 μm in **(VI.c)**. Adapted with permission.^[97] Copyright 2010, John Wiley & Sons. **(VII)** Bioprinting of an aortic valve conduit. **(VII.a)** Micro-CT reconstruction (green: valve root; red: valve leaflets). **(VII.b and c)** Schematic illustration of the bioprinting process. **(VII.b)** Root region of the first layer. **(VII.c)** Leaflet region of the first layer. **(VII.d)** Fluorescence image of two layers of an aortic valve conduit. Cells for valve root were labeled with cell tracker green and cells for valve leaflet with cell tracker red. Scale bar is 3 mm. **(VII.e)** Bioprinted aortic valve conduit. Adapted with permission.^[100] Copyright 2012, John Wiley and Sons. **(VIII)** 3D printed rigid filament networks of carbohydrate glass as a cytocompatible sacrificial template to obtain living cylindrical networks. The engineered networks allowed to align endothelial cells, while being perfused with blood. Cells expressing EGFP (green) were encapsulated in a variety of ECM materials, and imaged with confocal microscopy: matrix (red beads), cells (green), and perfusable vascular lumen (blue beads), as shown schematically (bottom right). The different materials with varied crosslinking mechanisms (above images) were all able to be patterned with vascular channels. Scale bars are 200 μm . Adapted with permission.^[99] Copyright 2012, Springer Nature. **(IX)** 3D printing of tough and biocompatible PEG–alginate–nanoclay hydrogels with multiple shapes (from left to right): hollow cube, hemisphere, pyramid, twisted bundle, and human ear and nose. Scale bars are 2 cm. Adapted with permission.^[102] Copyright 2015, John Wiley & Sons. **(X)** 3D bioprinting of vascularized constructs. **(X.a)** Schematic view and **(X.b and c)** fluorescence images of the proposed construct cultured for 0 and 2 days, respectively. Red and green filaments correspond to channels lined with red fluorescent protein-expressing HUVECs and green fluorescent protein-expressing human neonatal dermal fibroblast (HNFs) cell-laden gelMA ink, respectively. The cross-sectional view shows that endothelial cells line the lumens within the embedded 3D microvascular network. Scale bar is 300 μm . Adapted with permission.^[98] Copyright 2014, John Wiley & Sons.

3. Bringing multifunctionality to cell encapsulation systems

3.1 Stimuli-responsive strategies

To sustain life and maintain biological function, nature requires selectively tailored and adaptive molecular assemblies and interfaces that provide a specific chemical function and structure.^[105] Based on that, different stimuli-responsive and “adaptive” systems that are capable of conformational and chemical changes upon external stimulation are being developed. These changes are accompanied by variations in the physical properties of the polymeric chains of the hydrogel matrix or on other components, such as embedded particles and functionalized membranes. The signal is derived from changes in the matrix environment, such as in temperature, pH, chemical composition, and mechanical force, or it can be triggered externally by light-irradiation or exposure to an electrical/magnetic field. All the referred stimuli are widely used in drug delivery systems, in which pH and redox stimuli are the most common, since they exist naturally in certain pathological sites, for example the acidic environment of tumors.^[106,107] However, being the focus of the present review cell encapsulation strategies for tissue regeneration, only temperature-, light-, and magnetic-responsive stimuli will be discussed.

3.1.1 Temperature-responsive cell encapsulation systems

The most widely used temperature-responsive systems are related with the crosslinking process to fabricate *in situ* forming hydrogels. Those hydrogels are composed by thermoresponsive polymers that exhibit a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) and form a gel (sol-gel transition) upon temperature increase.^[108] Being a physical crosslinking, the process is reversible and the gel liquefies again when the temperature is lowered below the

LCST. Temperature-responsive hydrogels based on natural (alginate, chitosan, cellulose derivatives, gelatin, hyaluronic acid) and synthetic polymers (e.g., N-isopropyl acrylamide (NIPAm), poly(ethylene oxide)-*b*-poly(propylene oxide)-*b*-poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO-PPO-PEO) triblock copolymers, PEG-biodegradable polyester copolymers, poly(organophosphazenes) and 2-(dimethylamino) ethyl methacrylate) have been proposed for biomedical applications.^[109-111] The theories and mechanisms behind thermogelation have already been very well summarized elsewhere.^[109] Temperature-responsive systems are of particular interest in biomedical applications, mainly because their liquid state allow minimal invasive implantation by injection, and then gelation occurs by the increased physiological temperature of the body. Additionally, after injection, the hydrogel can easily adapt and match the different and complex conformations of the lesion sites. Some of the challenges with this type of hydrogels involve the precise control of the LCST, gelation kinetics, stability, mechanical properties, and degradation profiles. Syneresis is a major problem observed in some temperature-responsive systems, being mainly reported for NIPAm hydrogels. Syneresis is characterized by high amounts of water expel from the hydrogel matrix after gelation. A drastic water content decrease can change the shape of the hydrogel, and consequently interfere with their ability to match the lesion site due to shrinkage. Additionally, it can impair the diffusion mechanism of essential molecules, and thus compromise the viability of the encapsulated cells.^[112] As an attempt to overcome this drawback, biodegradable methacrylated thermogelling macromers (MA-TGMs) have been proposed.^[113] MA-TGMs are made from a statistical copolymer of NIPAm, acrylamide, and mono-acryloxyethyl phosphate (MAEP) that are esterified with glycidyl methacrylate after polymerization to yield dual-gelling macromers. These macromers are particularly promising for cell encapsulation applications, as they facilitate biointegration and degradation via hydrolysis of the phosphate ester bonds of MAEP. Hydrolysis of phosphate ester bonds of MAEP is accelerated in the presence of alkaline phosphatase, which is upregulated in bone regenerative sites. Hydrogels that readily undergo enzymatic degradation have demonstrated improved bone growth and infiltration.^[114] High and low MAEP were selected for *in vitro* and *in vivo* characterization to evaluate their potential to encapsulate MSCs and regenerate bone tissue.^[115] Results showed that functionalized hydrogels were able to induce bone growth, accelerate mineralization, and facilitate bone integration on a critical-size rat cranial defect. Different studies have also shown the conjugation of poly-NIPAm (pNIPAm) with a variety of hydrophilic polymers. PNIPAAm was conjugated with the natural polymer hyaluronic acid (HA) and pluripotent stem cells were encapsulated, including human hiPSCs and embryonic stem cells, while maintaining their pluripotency for several passages (4-6 passages).^[116] The stiffness and LCST of the hydrogel could be controlled by varying the molecular weight of HA, the concentration of the polymer, and the incorporation of hydrophobic groups into the pNIPAm chains. This is of great importance for stem cells encapsulation, since stiffness has been reported to affect stem cell proliferation and differentiation.^[117-121] Additionally, thiol-terminated PEG chains were attached to the HA-pNIPAm homopolymer as a proof-of-concept to demonstrate the feasibility of the hydrogel to be improved in terms of biological performance by chemically functionalization with proteins or peptides. pNIPAm has been also introduced into the backbone of many other natural polymers, such as alginate to produce monodisperse particles by microfluidics,^[122] and methacryloyl covalently-modified chitosan for an improved mechanical performance.^[123] Le Maitre and co-workers conjugated pNIPAm with N,N'-dimethylacrylamide and Laponite[®] clay nanoparticles to demonstrate *in vitro* the differentiation of encapsulated MSCs into nucleus pulposus (NP)-like cells in basal cell culture conditions, i.e. without adding chondrogenic differentiation medium or additional growth factors.^[124] The clinical success of the hydrogel was further demonstrated after minimal invasive injection (26G needle) into bovine NP tissue explants.^[125] After implantation, the hydrogel filled micro and macro fissures and provided mechanical support after restoring disc height. Importantly, the encapsulated MSCs differentiated and produced NP matrix components, and promoted the integration of the hydrogel with native NP tissue. In another study, pNIPAm was conjugated with poly(ethylene glycol) dimethacrylate (PEG-DMA) and incorporated within poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) electrospun fibers to construct a hybrid strategy for chondrogenesis of human MSCs.^[126] After cell seeding and incubation at 37°C, the thermosensitive hydrogel component of the hybrid scaffold quickly dissolved and filled the pores within the fiber structure. This led to a quick and mold-less single-step cell encapsulation strategy with superior mechanical properties compared to hydrogels alone. Despite its interesting behavior, pNIPAm has some limitations for *in vivo* applications because the monomer is carcinogenic/teratogenic, the isopropylamines resulted from degradation are toxic, and the polymer backbone is non-biodegradable. On the other hand, poly(N-vinylcaprolactam)

(PNVCL) does not produce toxic compounds when degraded and has demonstrated improved cell viability compared to pNIPAm.^[127] PNVCL hydrogels were already successfully tested for cartilage tissue engineering upon chondrocytes and MSCs encapsulation.^[128] Similar to pNIPAm, are the elastin-like polypeptides (ELPs) with a sol-gel transition at 34°C, first reported by Urry.^[129] Different cell encapsulation systems using ELPs have been recently described elsewhere.^[110,130]

The thermal-responsive ability of polymers can also be used to induce porosity in the hydrogel matrix. The principle of the process is the opposite on *in situ* gelation of hydrogels, i.e. the polymers employed are in gel state at low temperatures and become liquid when the temperature increases. Gelatin is frequently employed to fabricate those types of cell encapsulation systems. At 4°C a hydrogel matrix is formed, and at physiological temperature it becomes a liquid. Based on that, alginate hydrogels incorporating gelatin microbeads as porogens were proposed.^[131] The creation of pores inside the alginate hydrogel matrix was mediated by the dissolution of gelatin microparticles after incubation at 37°C. This thermo-responsive hydrogel architecture resulted in increased cell proliferation compared to alginate hydrogels without the gelatin microbeads. In a similar approach, gelatin microbeads were used both as chondrocytes carriers and porogens in alginate hydrogels.^[132] The gelatin microbeads were completely dissolved after two days of incubation at 37°C. Subsequently, the encapsulated chondrocytes occupied the created empty spaces within the alginate matrix and formed viable aggregates. Other shapes of such sacrificial elements could be explored, including fibers or branched structures to allow culture medium or blood perfusion across the hydrogel.

Temperature-responsive polymers can also be used to functionalize the hydrogel matrix and improve specific important features for the success of cell encapsulation strategies, such as proliferation and/or differentiation. For example, the triblock copolymer PEO-PPO-PEO, a class of synthetic materials with thermally responsive properties, was conjugated with transforming growth factor (TGF)- β 1 to induce the chondrogenic differentiation of encapsulated ASCs^[133] or with the arginine-glycine-aspartic acid (RGD) peptide sequence, a ubiquitous cell-binding domain found in many ECM molecules, well-known to mediate and enhance cell attachment to the hydrogel matrix.^[134] Others, have prepared a poly(ethylene glycol)-*b*-poly(*L*-alamine) hydrogel loaded with tauroursodeoxycholic acid (TUDCA), hepatocyte growth factor, and fibroblast growth factor 4 for the encapsulation of tonsil-derived MSCs.^[135] Remarkably, the injectable hydrogel was able to release TUDCA and the growth factors up to 21 days post-encapsulation. The incorporation of biomolecules within the matrix of hydrogels to modulate the behavior of the encapsulated cells will be discussed in section 3.2 *Incorporation of bioactive molecules*. Synthetic polypeptide-based temperature-responsive hydrogels have been conjugated with PEG, poly(vinyl pyrrolidone), and the triblock copolymer ABA of poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO, block A) and poly(propylene oxide, block B), commercially available as Pluronics®. Those systems have been proposed for cell encapsulation as recently reviewed elsewhere.^[110]

On the other hand, instead of functionalizing the encapsulation matrix with biomolecules, Matrigel™ has been used to encapsulate cells since it contains a plethora of basement membrane components of collagens, laminin, entactin and heparan sulfate, proteoglycan, bFGF, epidermal growth factor (EGF), IGF-1, platelet-derived growth factor, nerve growth factor, TGF- β , among other biochemical components not fully identified.^[136-140] However, Matrigel™ is limited to *in vitro* applications, since it derives from the Engelbreth-Holm-Swarm (EHS) sarcoma.

Others, took advantage of the polymeric structure of biomaterials to induce temperature-responsive ability. A great example is the linear cationic polysaccharide, chitosan (CHT). CHT has been used to produce hydrogels through crosslinking of free amino groups. However, CHT requires an acidic environment to solubilize, thus mild conditions required for cell encapsulation are not assured. By controlling the N-acetylation degree of amino group in the polymer chain, CHT can be water-soluble. However, only a few studies using water-soluble CHT as the encapsulation matrix have been reported.^[141,142] A simple and interesting strategy to become CHT water-soluble is to combine with β -glycerophosphate (β GP), which also confers temperature-responsive ability, as first proposed elsewhere.^[143] It is suggested that as the temperature increases a proton is transferred from CHT to the phosphate moiety of β GP, consequently leading to gelation of the aqueous CHT/ β GP solution.^[144] For the encapsulation of cells, CHT/ β GP has been proposed alone^[51] or combined with other materials, such as bioactive glass nanoparticles,^[145] collagen,^[146,147] gelatin,^[148] hydroxyapatite,^[149] hydroxyethyl cellulose,^[150] starch,^[151] among others.

Another example of the contribution of a temperature-responsive polymer to enhance specific properties of the hydrogel matrix uses thermosensitive microparticles composed by poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) and PEG within PEO-PPO-PEO hydrogels.^[152] When the temperature increased to physiological levels, the microparticles became cohesive and adhered to each other. Then, the hydrophilic environment provided by the temperature-responsive PEO-PPO-PEO hydrogel caused leaching of PEG microparticles. Consequently, with the release of PEG to the hydrogel matrix, its mechanical properties were significantly enhanced. Any assay with encapsulated cells was performed, but the authors suggest its applicability for growth factors incorporation and/or cell encapsulation due to the mild conditions of the process. Due to the observed high mechanical strength, future studies with this hydrogel should focus on its osteogenic potential for bone regeneration applications.

3.1.2 Light-activated cell encapsulation systems

Similar to temperature-responsive strategies for *in situ* crosslinking, light-responsive hydrogels are also of particular interest in biomedical applications requiring *in situ* non-toxic gelation, such as cell encapsulation strategies. The principle in light-responsive hydrogel crosslinking is based on the presence of free radicals that lead to the fast formation of covalent bonds between macromolecular precursor molecules, resulting in the formation of a polymer network with uniform and replicable physical properties.^[153,154] Long-wave UV light-activated polymerization is one of the most common methods of forming cell encapsulation strategies because of the advantages of temporal and spatial control of the reaction, low energy requirements, and clinically acceptable curing times.^[155] Photopolymerization can thus be easily performed at physiological temperature and pH, while enabling the implantation of photopolymerized hydrogels encapsulating cells by minimally invasive procedures. The critical aspects to consider in photopolymerized hydrogel in cell encapsulation are the required non-toxicity of the photoinitiator (PI) and the irradiation with an appropriate wavelength and time. As the PI incorporated within the hydrogel matrix is irradiated with light, free radicals dissociate from the PI and attack with high efficiency vinyl groups on precursor macromolecules, creating covalent bonds that rapidly promote the crosslink within seconds to minutes of UV light exposure. However, photoinitiator solutions associated with free-radical generation can lead to cell toxicity.^[156] Therefore, some critical shortcomings related with the use of PIs in cell encapsulation strategies, including its limited water solubility, sub-optimal crosslinking efficiency when applied with safe light spectra (i.e. ≥ 350 nm), and the toxic reaction conditions of the free radicals must be considered before designing cell encapsulation strategies.^[157] Consequently, among the many initiator systems available for photopolymerization, only a few have been identified as suitable for cell encapsulation systems. Studies providing a better understanding of the interplay between the radical crosslinking efficiency, hydrogel network formation, and cytotoxicity using photopolymerized hydrogels for cell encapsulating are thus of extreme importance. Hydrogels were photopolymerized from PEG-DA or PEG-fibrinogen precursors using different Irgacure PIs, together with the chemical initiator/accelerator ammonium persulfate/tetramethylethylenediamine.^[154] The study evaluated the influence of PI type, concentration and UV light intensity, and how these affected the mechanical properties of the hydrogel, the crosslinking reaction time and the viability of encapsulated cells. For this purpose, a biosynthetic hybrid hydrogel synthesized from functionalized PEG conjugated to fibrinogen and encapsulating bovine aortic smooth muscle cells (SMCs) was used. The photoinitiators I2959 and I184 were identified as suitable for achieving both cell viability and efficient crosslinking, contrary to the results obtained with I651. Optimization of PI concentration or irradiation intensity was particularly important for achieving maximum mechanical properties; a sub-optimal choice of PI concentration or irradiation intensity resulted in a substantial reduction in the elastic modulus. The viability of the encapsulated SMCs may be compromised by unnecessarily prolonging exposure to cytotoxic free radicals or inadvertently enhancing the instantaneous dose of radicals in solution, both of which are dependent on the PI type/concentration and irradiation intensity. In the absence of a radical initiator, the short exposures to long-wave UV light irradiation did not prove to be cytotoxic. I2959 photoinitiator was used to yield the crosslinking of DEXT-MA hydrogels.^[158] L929 cells were suspended in the DEXT-MA solution and dispensed on the surface of the SH surfaces. Due to surface repellency, spherical drops were obtained, which were then crosslinked using UV-light. Subsequently, the microbeads were encapsulated in alginate hydrogels using again the SH surfaces. This type of photo-responsive strategy allowed creating a multicompartmentalized cell encapsulation strategy. These types of cell encapsulation systems

will be discussed in detail in section 3.3 *Multicompartmentalization*.

In a different perspective, photo-responsive cell encapsulation systems can be used to control specific properties of the hydrogel matrix, such as its degradation. This strategy emerges as an alternative to hydrolysis and enzymolysis, the two most commonly used mechanisms to control hydrogel degradation. Although both mechanisms are effective, the rate of degradation cannot be adjusted or arrested after the hydrogel is fabricated. Additionally, the degradation of hydrogels occurring by hydrolysis and enzymolysis cannot be spatially controlled. In contrast, photodegradation allows external real-time spatial and temporal control over hydrogel properties.^[159-162] This represents a great advantage for cell encapsulation strategies aiming tissue regeneration, because the properties of the encapsulation matrix can be tailored to match the time required for the natural regeneration process of the damaged tissue. For example, different macromers were synthesized incorporating photodegradable *ortho*-nitrobenzyl (*o*-NB) groups in the macromer backbone.^[163] To show the applicability of the synthesized hydrogels to encapsulated cells, human mesenchymal stem cells were used. Results showed high viability rates. By exploiting the differences in reactivity of different *o*-NB linkers, the degradation rate of the hydrogels could be precisely controlled.

Others have proposed controlling the material properties of hydrogels both dynamically and in a user defined fashion using cleavable chemistries whose degradation can be triggered exogenously. Toward this end, different groups have presented a class of photodegradable hydrogels whose physical and chemical properties can be modified by light post-fabrication with full spatial and temporal control.^[159,160,164] Within the TERM field, those hydrogels are particularly interesting since they allow controlling the extracellular microenvironment in the presence of cells in 3D, while providing insights of the microenvironment in real time.^[160-162, 165,166]

3.1.3 Magnetic-responsive cell encapsulation systems

While the majority of temperature- and light-responsive cell encapsulation systems emerged as *in situ* crosslinking strategies, magnetic-responsive cell encapsulation systems have emerged as a new strategy to manipulate and/or stimulate cell encapsulation systems. This strategy exploits interactions between encapsulation devices and magnetic fields that can be either static^[167] or alternating fields established by a magnet^[168] or electromagnet.^[169] Magnetic assembly of cell encapsulating systems into 3D structures has been recently reported for TERM.^[94,95,169-171] Specifically, magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) have been loaded in cell-encapsulating microscale hydrogels (M-gels) to create composite smart materials responsive to magnetic fields. As an example, gelMA hydrogels were produced co-encapsulating 3T3 cells and MNPs.^[94] By spatially controlling the magnetic field, these composite hydrogel building blocks could be manipulated to construct 3D structures with variable geometries, as well as to control the composition of the hydrogel matrix by creating multilayers. MNPs have also been used to stimulate encapsulated stem cells into a specific differentiation lineage. This can be achieved by manipulation or mechanical activation of cellular pathways, such as the mechanogated potassium channel TREK-1, and integrin signaling such as the RGD transmembrane protein, which have been showed to enhance the osteogenic and chondrogenic potential of magnetic labeled bone marrow MSCs encapsulated in alginate/chitosan spherical hydrogels.^[172] Others, have showed to enhance the chondrogenic potential of ASCs encapsulated in κ -carrageenan hydrogels containing within its matrix MNPs.^[173]

In order to physically isolate the co-encapsulated cells and MNPs, different multicompartmentalized strategies were proposed,^[174-176] which will be further discussed in detail (section 3.3 *Multicompartmentalization*). A major concern of incorporating MNPs in the cell encapsulation matrix is their release as the hydrogel degrades, although it was demonstrated that the released MNPs from gelMA hydrogels had no adverse effect on the viability of NIH 3T3 cells.^[177] However, because of the risk of heavy metal poisoning from iron oxide, the use of such MNPs in clinical applications has to be proven. Additionally, the distribution of MNPs in M-gels may differ due to aggregation of the MNPs in the pre-polymeric solutions, which may reduce the affinity of M-gels to the magnetic field (MF).^[178,179] Another potential drawback with this method is that a certain amount of heat generated by MNPs exposure to an alternating current-based MF (magnetic hyperthermia) may compromise the viability of the encapsulated cells.^[171]

Alternatives without integrating hydrogels with other magnetic components, such as MNPs, were successfully proposed using their paramagnetic free radicals when placed in a magnetic

field.^[94,180,181] Radicals can be utilized to change the magnetic susceptibility of liquids on each the levitation of structures is performed (suspension liquids) or they can be directly incorporated in the encapsulation matrix for guided levitational self-assembly.^[181] Magnetization of the TE systems via free radicals is a versatile and robust strategy, and cell encapsulation can be performed before radical exposure for magnetization.

The magnetic manipulation of fibers was also reported to control and align fibers into specific patterns.^[182,183] This hierarchical organization allows the hydrogel matrix to take a variety of forms in different tissues and at different stages of development in the same tissue. Moreover, the biological assemblies, disassembly and re-assembly are dynamic during the transition to accomplish local and global conformational changes. Additionally, with this strategy it is possible to guide the cell growth at specific directions by regulating the magnetic fibers.

3.2 Incorporation of bioactive molecules

Interactions of cells and ECM initiate signaling cascades involved in critical cell functions, such as regeneration.^[184-186] An important goal of cell encapsulation systems aiming tissue regeneration is to mimic critical aspects of the extracellular environment in order to ensure the viability of the encapsulated cells while controlling different cellular functions through cell-material interactions. This prompted the encapsulation of cells with biomolecules, which encompass nowadays a major area of investigation in TERM and regenerative medicine field. Challenges of this strategy include all the well-known critical properties of cell encapsulation strategies, namely permeability, degradability, biocompatibility, stability, and sterile conditions, with the addition of critical properties to develop systems incorporating biomolecules, such as the bioactivity preservation and a sustained release. Additionally, when designing these types of combined systems, the incorporation of biomolecules at the right concentration in the right context and, when aimed, release with the right profile must be carefully pondered. The incorporation of different biomolecules can be directly within the biomaterials employed or indirectly by first encapsulating the biomolecule in micro- or nano-sized spheres (particles or beads) or fibers, which are then embedded in the system.

Encapsulation of biomolecules directly in the core of the cell encapsulation system is easily achieved during gelation and provides a simple way to entrap molecules of interest. For example, TGF- β 1 was co-encapsulated with Sca-1⁺/CD45⁻ cardiac progenitor cells (CPCs) in high molecular weight heparin-containing hyaluronic acid-based hydrogels.^[187] Results showed that TGF- β 1 was able to induce the differentiation of CPCs into endothelial cells, which formed vascular-like networks within the hydrogel. Due to the electrostatic association between heparin and TGF- β 1, which was enhanced due to the high molecular weight of heparin, a portion of the initially encapsulated growth factor remains immobile. Therefore, TGF- β 1 could be provided to the encapsulated cells since it did not diffuse out from the hydrogel. In fact, the rapid loss of the entrapped biomolecule from the system is a major concern when direct encapsulation methodology is employed. Consequently, this method is more appropriate for molecules in a limited molecular weight range (i.e., similar to the network mesh size), and those that are relatively stable and have a long half-life. Therefore, indirect entrapment of biomolecules is more often used in TERM strategies. For example, TGF- β 3 was encapsulated in gelatin beads, which were subsequently incorporated in a collagen-low molecular weight hyaluronic acid semi-interpenetrating network encapsulating MSCs. This injectable system supported *in vitro* and *in vivo* the growth of nasal chondrocytes and chondrogenic differentiation and MSCs, and was proposed for nucleus pulposus regeneration.^[188] In a similar strategy, but using fibers as drug carriers, electrospun polycaprolactone (PCL) nanofibers were used as drug carriers of bovine serum albumin.^[189] The nanofibers were then embedded in PEG hydrogel encapsulating fibroblasts. In the case of indirect methods, a complex coacervation methodology was recently proposed in order to eliminate the step of encapsulating the biomolecule within drug carriers previous to its addition to the cell encapsulating system.^[190] Complex coacervation is defined as liquid-liquid phase separation in an aqueous solution by spontaneous aggregation associated with electrostatic matching between two oppositely charged polyelectrolytes.^[191] Based on that, coacervate-laden photo-crosslinked hydrogels were produced from the simple mixing of oxidized methacrylated alginate (OMA) and gelMA in aqueous solution. Bone morphogenic protein (BMP)-2 was incorporated in the gelMA solution, which mainly comprised the resulting coacervate microdroplets, and MSCs in OMA. Within the resultant compartments, MSCs differentiated into the osteogenic lineage due to the internal sustained release of BMP-2. Combined direct and indirect encapsulation of biomolecules was achieved by embedding PLGA microparticles within the matrix of alginate hydrogels through a coaxial electro-dropping

method.^[30] Two different osteogenic biomolecules, namely BMP-2 and dexamethasone (Dex), were co-encapsulated with bone marrow MSCs. Consequently, two different co-encapsulation systems were produced by switching the position of BMP-2 and Dex, either in the PLGA microparticles or in the alginate matrix. Based on the localization of BMP-2 and Dex, their release profiles were very unique on a temporal basis. An initial burst of biomolecules was highly suppressed when either biomolecule was loaded in the PLGA core. Therefore, the release profiles of each biomolecule could be easily manipulated alternately positioning biomolecules in the embedded microparticles or in the hydrogel matrix domain. Alternatively to large biomolecules and growth factors encapsulation, biochemical signals can also be integrated by incorporating smaller molecules, such as peptides, in cell encapsulation systems, targeting a desired cellular response. MSCs were induced to differentiate towards osteogenic or adipogenic pathways by introducing in PEG hydrogels tethered small-molecule chemical functional groups, namely 2-aminoethyl methacrylate, *t*-butyl methacrylate, ethylene glycol methacrylate phosphate, 2,2,3,3-tetrafluoropropyl methacrylate and methacrylic acid.^[192] In response to the small-molecule incorporated, encapsulated MSCs changed its morphology and differentiated in the absence of soluble signals, thus highlighting the crucial role that cell-material interactions have in cell fate.

Another study developed an agarose hydrogel with a concentration gradient of immobilized vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)-165.^[193] By mimicking the cues that guide endothelial cells (ECs) during vascular development, ECs were shown to follow the concentration gradient of VEGF-165 in the 3D hydrogel, with the identification of tip and stalk cells and the formation of tubular-like structures. Furthermore, the stem cell differentiation could be controlled in the developed 3D hydrogels by taking advantage of orthogonal physical binding pairs, such as barnase, an extracellular RNase of *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, with its intracellular inhibitor barstar, and streptavidin-biotin.^[194] This allowed the simultaneous immobilization of multiple growth factors.

In a different perspective, the encapsulated cells can also release different biotherapeutics itself, which in fact constitute the first impetus when cell encapsulation systems were proposed. However, in the present review, the biotherapeutics release ability of encapsulated cells will not be addressed (for that subject we advise the reading elsewhere^[195]), as here we intend to review the multifunctionality of cell encapsulation systems on a material engineering basis.

Another strategy currently being explored by a great number of studies is the incorporation of ECM for tissue engineering applications,^[196] and in particular within the scope of the present review, for hydrogels.^[197] ECM, the non-cellular component of all tissues and organs, is not just an inert scaffold that provides physical support, but instead can profoundly influence cell fate choices through crucial biochemical and biomechanical cues required for tissue morphogenesis, differentiation, and homeostasis.^[198,199] Given the importance of ECM in directing cells performance current research has been growing interest in the development of systems incorporating decellularized tissues as an abundant source of tissue-specific ECM. However, scaffolds composed solely from decellularized ECM are limited in terms of tuning biomechanical properties to control cell-cell and cell-ECM interaction.^[200] As an alternative, a methodology that incorporates cryo-milled decellularized tissues within hydrogels was proposed.^[201] Decellularized tissues from human adipose tissue and porcine auricular cartilage were used to produce ECM particles and then incorporated within different hydrogels methacrylated chondroitin sulphate hydrogels UV-initiated and thermally induced crosslinked. The encapsulated adipose-derived stem cells remained highly viable and their differentiation fate towards adipo- or chondrogenic lineage could be controlled just by varying the type of ECM particles embedded. Others, used gelMA hydrogels incorporating by covalent bound a methacrylated matrix composed by decellularized mixtures of cartilage, meniscus, and tendon tissues.^[202] Besides natural polymers, also synthetic polymers have been used to produce decellularized hybrid hydrogels. For example, PEG was conjugated with decellularized myocardial matrix either by crosslinking the proteins with an amine-reactive PEG-star or by photo-induced radical polymerization of two different multi-armed PEG acrylates.^[203] It was shown that the synthesized hybrid hydrogels still contained a nanofibrous network similar to native myocardial matrix, and that the fiber diameter could be controlled by the method of PEG incorporation and molecular weight. Others, combined decellularized Wharton's jelly with polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) hydrogels for cartilage regeneration.^[204]

3.3 Multicompartmentalization

Inspired by the natural multicompartmentalized complex system of cells, in which a wide range

of isolated components with specific functions are grouped together in a single compartment, different miniaturized compartmental engineered systems have been proposed in fields such as catalysis, sensors, drug delivery, microreactors, and theoretical models of cellular events and diseases.^[205-209] The idea is “to borrow Nature’s design strategies to achieve novel functional materials, with highly useful properties exceeding by far those available by current methods”,^[210] but “not to copy Biology: learning in modesty from her principles and to transfer it to materials space and conditions previously not accessible to biology”.^[211] Inspired by that, and particularly for cell encapsulation systems, the idea is not to mimic intracellular reactions, but rather construct a customizable system by assembling sub compartments to ultimately giving rise to a complex system with improved cell viability and functionality. Different groups have recently begun to explore the field and its application in TERM. For example, Janus particles, i.e. anisotropic particles that contain distinct compositions in each hemisphere, were proposed to physically isolate encapsulated cells from iron oxide nanoparticles or a drug in the second compartment.^[176] Alginate Janus particles, produced in a septum-theta capillary device, were composed by one magnetic hemisphere with nanoparticles, and one hemisphere with MSCs. This kind of strategies are proposed as an alternative to magnetic labeling of cells via uptake of surface functionalized magnetic beads, which can lead to undesirable effects on cells.^[212] Also aiming to physically isolate cells from MNPs, a capsule-in-capsule system was proposed for the treatment of diabetes.^[174] The idea was to confer to the cell encapsulation system the ability to be detectable by clinically applicable non-invasive imaging modalities, such as magnetic resonance, computed tomography, and ultrasound imaging, in order to monitor over time and assess the efficacy of islets transplantation and engraftment. However, a high concentration of iron and gold nanoparticles is required to achieve a sufficient amount of contrast signal to be detectable by the referred methods, which could be harmful to the encapsulated cells. Therefore, nanoparticles were encapsulated in a primary inner capsule of alginate, and then added to a secondary outer capsule containing the therapeutic islets cells. Also using MNPs, three-layer spheroids composed by magnetic gelMA M-gels encapsulating NIH 3T3 cells were fabricated onto the tip of a magnetic rod.^[94] Three fluorochromes, namely rhodamine-B (red) in the first layer, FITC-dextran (green) in the second layer, and 1,1,4,4-tetraphenyl-1,3-butadiene (blue) in the third layer, were used as a proof-of-concept to show that three different compartments could be easily created (in seconds) by magnetic manipulation. Each layer was stabilized via a second crosslinking procedure using filling layers of PEG. A filling layer between multiple M-gels permitted to increase cell-cell distances and thus isolate the different layer compartments. A similar multicompartmentalized cell encapsulation strategy resembling “onion-like” structure using alginate and L929 cells was achieved without magnetic manipulation but using the unique repellency properties of SH surfaces.^[40] A remarkable advantage of this technique, especially when combining cell encapsulation with drug loading, is that high encapsulation efficiencies (of ca. 100%) of non-volatile molecules can be achieved under mild conditions. This is possible because each compartmentalized layer solidifies in air rather than in contact with a liquid solvent. Hence, one avoids the possibility of molecules migration, and thus any loss during the preparation of the particles. Others explored different spatial organization of compartmentalized layers inside a single cell encapsulation system by microfluidic electrostatic spraying technique.^[213] For that, cell encapsulation systems were produced using double layer, side-by-side or triple-layer conformities. In each compartment, different cells were encapsulated, each one fluorescently stained with different dyes. The system was tested for different potential applications, such as size-controlled tumor micro tissues and its implications in cancer diagnostics, and a scalable platform for 3D co-culture. Similarly to multilayered spherical systems, also multilayered fiber-shaped systems have been reported for cell encapsulation.^[69,80] Core-shell hydrogel fibers were successfully generated using the dual concentric nozzle by the simultaneous injection of collagen and alginate solutions in the core and shell, respectively.^[80] By encapsulating MCs, osteoblasts, and bioactive glass nanoparticles (BGn) were also incorporated within the multilayered fibers. By varying the position and presence of the encapsulated cells and BGn within the fibers compartments, different formulations could be obtained. In a higher scale level, such fibers could be organized into more complex 3D shapes using established rapid prototyping methods.

In a different perspective, compartmentalization was used to avoid protrusion of the encapsulated cells.^[39] In the proposed system, alginate with different mechanical stabilities was used to facilitate growth of the cells in the core of the capsules, but to kill cells that might escape from the capsule and invade the host. For that, 3.4% intermediate-G alginate was employed to

fabricate the core encapsulating cells, while 2% high-G alginate was employed in the outer layer, since it was showed to jeopardize cell survival.

It is expected that advances in bottom-up and top-down technologies will originate the development of new hierarchical and complex structures with sophisticated geometries,^[214] as well as production on a massive scale and a wider clinical application of those systems.

4. Conclusions and future perspectives

Since the early pioneering period, cell encapsulation has developed significantly in such a way that it is now one of the most used technologies among the scientific community in TERM. The application of cell encapsulation principles in the TERM field brought new possibilities for the development of highly complex 3D cell culture systems. Although widely used, such systems for tissue regeneration still hold tremendous promise. The new generation of such systems integrates within its design recent molecular biology breakthroughs, such as its combination with cells from the immune system. This allows increasing the complexity of the systems by recreating adequate environmental signals found in native tissue (in particular during the regenerative process) to control the cellular outcome, and conferring multifunctional properties, namely the incorporation of bioactive molecules and the ability to create smart and adaptive systems in response to different stimuli. In parallel, advances in the production methods and characterization techniques, especially microscopy techniques, have contributed for the improved performance of these systems.

Yet many challenges remain. The stepwise analysis of the essential obstacles, coupled with increased collaboration between expertise laboratories, should move the technology forward and bring it much closer to the development of devices with clinical application. Prior to the design of a cell encapsulation system, scientists have to deal with different critical properties that dictate the success of the strategy. This render the “closed scaffolds” in opposition to “open scaffolds” (scaffolds at which seeded cells adhere to a surface and are able to contact with the external milieu) in a more complex designing area. In “open scaffolds” the production methods can comprise a wide range of precursors and harsh solvents and/or reactants as long as the final scaffold is cytocompatible, including its degradation products. On the other hand, in “closed scaffolds” mild production methods must be employed due to the presence of cells, which is also a significant limitation in terms of available technologies and suitable biomaterials that can be processed at those conditions. Besides mild conditions, cell encapsulation strategies must assure sterile conditions, an adequate permeability of essential molecules and waste products, stability and degradation of the system coupled with the regeneration of the target tissue, and biocompatibility/biotolerability. Despite the current challenges, “closed scaffolds” can offer several advantages over “open scaffolds” for TERM. Overall, they (i) allow to create an optimized microenvironment for cells and protect them from an undesirable severe immunological response by avoiding the entrance of immune cells; (ii) are compatible with *in situ* injectable strategies, in which cells are suspended in a liquid precursor solution and delivered *in vivo* to the site of interest. By curing the hydrogel directly at the lesion site, the precursor solution can diffuse into the entire volume of the defect, leading to an enhanced integration of the scaffolds without requiring glue or sutures, as the formed hydrogel can easily adapt to the defect geometry; (iii) multiple compartments or elements with distinct functions can be easily grouped in one single structure, conferring multifunctionality to the engineered system as well as facilitating *in vitro* handling and *in vivo* implantation procedures over dealing with various ungrouped materials; and (iv) if desirable, the implant can be easily removed after treatment. Ultimately, for a cell encapsulation strategy to be applied successfully in TERM, a number of practical factors must be considered in addition to the critical properties discussed above. The process must be easily scaled up for manufacturing, marketable, and accepted by surgeons, patients, and healthcare providers, and ultimately receive approval from the competent authorities, such as the FDA and equivalents. This ambitious goal requires the interdisciplinary and integrated effort of scientists with different areas of expertise from materials science to pharmaceutical technology. Issues on long term cell viability, the integration of the implanted materials with the existing tissues, risk of an acute immune response leading to the formation of a fibrous capsule, together with the above-referred systems requirements, should be addressed to further explore their possible clinical applications. On the other hand, it is then easy to understand why the emerging cell encapsulation systems have often a hierarchical and complex organization. To boost the technology and give a significative step towards the clinics, we believe that the interplay with

the immune system should be considered in the new generation of cell encapsulation systems. Different studies have been recently showing a favorable influence of macrophages on the regeneration of tissues. The main challenge is to design a cell encapsulation system that would allow not only to regenerate the target tissue, while simultaneously controlling intra- and intercellular mechanisms of the recruited immune cells. To achieve such goal is imperative to fully understand the complex role of immune cells in tissue regeneration. It is, thus, our conviction that immunomodulation should be incorporated within the design of the next generation of cell encapsulation systems. By achieving this and fully studying the system, we believe that we can then deconstruct its complexity and achieve more simple systems.

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References

- [1] V.V. Bisceglie, *Z. Krebsforsch.* **1933**, *40*, 141.
- [2] G.H. Algire, J.M. Weaver, R.T. Prehn, *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.* **1954**, *15*, 493.
- [3] T.M.S. Chang, *Science* **1964**, *146*, 524.
- [4] W.L. Chick, A.A. Like, V. Lauris, *Science* **1975**, *187*, 847.
- [5] D. Ferreira, E. Westman, H. Eyjolfssdottir, P. Almqvist, G. Lind, B. Linderroth, A. Seiger, K. Blennow, A. Karami, T. Darreh-Shori, M. Wiberg, A. Simmons, O. Wahlund, L. Wahlberg, M. Eriksdotter, *J. Alzheimers Dis.* **2015**, *43*, 1059.
- [6] R. Krishnan, M. Alexander, L. Robles, C.E Foster 3rd, J.R.T. Lakey, *Rev. Diabet. Stud.* **2014**, *11*, 84.
- [7] O. Lindvall, L. Wahlberg, *Exp. Neurol.* **2008**, *209*, 82.
- [8] F. Lim, A.M. Sun, *Science* **1980**, *210*, 908.
- [9] J. Koo, T. Chang, *Int. J. Artif. Organs* **1993**, *16*, 557.
- [10] P. Chang, N. Shen, A. Westcott, *Hum. Gene Ther.* **1993**, *4*, 433.
- [11] H. Liu, F. Ofosu, P. Chang, *Hum. Gene Ther.* **1993**, *4*, 291.
- [12] D. Cieslinski, H. Humes, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **1994**, *43*, 678.
- [13] H. Wong, T. Chang, *Int. J. Artif. Organs* **1986**, *9*, 335.
- [14] P. Aebischer, P. Russell, L. Christenson, G. Panol, J. Monchik, P. Galletti, *ASAIO J.* **1986**, *32*, 134.
- [15] P. Aebischer, M. Goddard, A. Signore, R. Timpson, *Exp. Neurol.* **1994**, *126*, 151.
- [16] F.B. Barton, M.R. Rickels, R. Alejandro, B.J. Hering, S. Wease, B. Naziruddin, J. Oberholzer, J.S. Odorico, M.R. Garfinkel, M. Levy, F. Pattou, T. Berney, A. Secchi, S. Messinger, P.A. Senior, P. Maffi, A. Posselt, P.G. Stock, D.B. Kaufman, X. Luo, F. Kandeel, E. Cagliero, N.A. Turgeon, P. Witkowski, A. Naji, P.J. O'Connell, C. Greenbaum, Y.C. Kudva, K.L. Brayman, M.J. Aull, C. Larsen, T.W. Kay, L.A. Fernandez, M.C. Vantyghem, M. Bellin, A.M. Shapiro, *Diabetes Care* **2012**, *35*, 1436.
- [17] A.K. Brun-Graepi, C. Richard, M. Bessodes, D. Scherman, O.W. Merten, *J. Controlled Release* **2011**, *149*, 209.
- [18] S. Mazzitelli, L. Capretto, F. Quinci, R. Piva, C. Nastruzzi, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2013**, *65*, 1533.
- [19] H. Tian, Z. Tang, X. Zhuang, X. Chen, X. Jing, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2012**, *37*, 237.
- [20] J. Wilson, T. McDevitt, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **2013**, *110*, 667.
- [21] A.S. Hoffman, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2012**, *64*, 18.
- [22] Z. Chen, T. Klein, R.Z. Murray, R. Crawford, J. Chang, C. Wu, Y. Xiao, *Mater. Today* **2016**, *19*, 304.
- [23] O. Veiseh, J.C. Doloff, M. Ma, A.J. Vegas, H.H. Tam, A.R. Bader, J. Li, E. Langan, J. Wyckoff, W.S. Loo, S. Jhunjhunwala, A. Chiu, S. Siebert, K. Tang, J. Hollister-Lock, S. Aresta-Dasilva, M. Bochenek, J. Mendonza-Elias, Y. Wang, M. Qi, D.M. Lavin, M., Chen, N. Dholakia, R. Thakrar, I. Lacík, G.C. Weir, J. Oberholzer, D.L. Greiner, R. Langer, D.G. Anderson, *Nat. Mater.* **2015**, *14*, 643.
- [24] H. Uludag, P. De Vos, P.A. Tresco, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2000**, *42*, 29.
- [25] B. Ríhová, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2000**, *42*, 65.
- [26] R. van Schilfgaarde, P. de Vos, *J. Mol. Med.* **1999**, *77*, 199.
- [27] P. de Vos, B. de Haan, J. Pater, R. van Schilfgaarde, *Transplantation* **1996**, *62*, 893.
- [28] R.M. Hernandez, G. Orive, A. Murua, J.L. Pedraz, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2010**, *62*, 711.

- [29] A.M.S. Costa, M. Alatorre-Meda, C. Alvarez-Lorenzo, J.F. Mano, *Small* **2015**, *11*, 3648.
- [30] D.H. Choi, C.H., Park, I.H., Kim, H.J. Chun, K. Park, D.K. Han, *J. Controlled Release* **2010**, *147*, 193.
- [31] S. Abang, E.S. Chan, D. Poncelet, *J. Microencapsul.* **2012**, *29*, 417.
- [32] E. Martins, D. Renard, J. Davy, M. Marquis, D. Poncelet, *J. Microencapsul.* **2015**, *32*, 86.
- [33] C.R. Correia, P. Sher, R.L. Reis, J.F. Mano, *Soft Matter* **2013**, *9*, 2125.
- [34] C.R. Correia, R.L. Reis, J.F. Mano, *Biomacromolecules* **2013**, *14*, 743.
- [35] C.R. Correia, R.P. Pirraco, M.T. Cerqueira, A.P. Marques, R.L. Reis, J.F. Mano, *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 21883.
- [36] C.R. Correia, S. Gil, R.L. Reis, J.F. Mano, *Adv. Healthcare Mater.* **2016**, *5*, 1346.
- [37] C.R. Correia, T.C. Santos, R.P. Pirraco, M.T. Cerqueira, A.P. Marques, R.L. Reis, J.F. Mano, *Acta Biomater.* **2017**, *53*, 483.
- [38] H. Zhou, H.H. Xu, *Biomaterials* **2011**, *32*, 7503.
- [39] S.V. Bhujbal, B. de Haan, S.P. Niclou, P. de Vos, *Sci. Rep.* **2014**, *4*, 6856.
- [40] A.C. Lima, C.A. Custodio, C. Alvarez-Lorenzo, J.F. Mano, *Small* **2013**, *9*, 2486.
- [41] N.L. Costa, P. Sher, J.F. Mano, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* **2011**, *13*, B218.
- [42] V. Kozlovskaya, S. Harbaugh, I. Drachuk, O. Shchepelina, N. Kelley-Loughnane, M. Stone, V.V. Tsukruk, *Soft Matter* **2011**, *7*, 2364.
- [43] A. Diaspro, D. Silvano, S. Krol, O. Cavalleri, A. Gliozzi, *Langmuir* **2002**, *18*, 5047.
- [44] A.E. Mayfield, E.L. Tilokee, N. Latham, B. McNeill, B.K. Lam, M. Ruel, E.J. Suuronen, D.W. Courtman, D.J. Stewart, D.R. Davis, *Biomaterials* **2014**, *35*, 133.
- [45] A. Blocki, S. Beyer, J.Y. Dewavrin, A. Goralczyk, Y. Wang, P. Peh, M. Ng, S.S. Moonshi, S. Vuddagiri, M. Raghunath, E.C. Martinez, K.K. Bhakoo, *Biomaterials* **2015**, *53*, 12.
- [46] M. Endres, N. Wenda, H. Woehlecke, K. Neumann, J. Ringe, C. Erggelet, D. Lerche, C. Kaps, *Acta Biomater.* **2010**, *6*, 436.
- [47] J.W. Andrejcsk, J. Cui, W.G. Chang, J. Devalliere, J.S. Pober, W.M. Saltzman, *Biomaterials* **2013**, *34*, 8899.
- [48] S. Utech, R. Prodanovic, A.S. Mao, R. Ostafe, D.J. Mooney, D.A. Weitz, *Adv. Healthcare Mater.* **2015**, *4*, 1628.
- [49] A.C. Lima, P. Batista, T.A. Valente, A.S. Silva, I.J. Correia, J.F. Mano, *Tissue Eng., Part A* **2013**, *19*, 1175.
- [50] R. Silva, R. Singh, B. Sarker, D.G. Papageorgiou, J.A. Juhasz, J.A. Roether, I. Cicha, J. Kaschta, D.W. Schubert, K. Chrissafis, R. Detsch, A.R. Boccaccini, *J. Mater. Chem. B* **2014**, *2*, 5441.
- [51] A.C. Lima, C.R. Correia, M.B. Oliveira, J.F. Mano, *J. Bioact. Compat. Polym.* **2014**, *29*, 50.
- [52] B.P. Chan, T.Y. Hui, M.Y. Wong, K.H.K. Yip, G.C.F. Chan, *Tissue Eng., Part C* **2010**, *16*, 225.
- [53] C.H. Li, T.K. Chik, A.H. Ngan, S.C. Chan, D.K. Shum, B.P. Chan, *Tissue Eng., Part A* **2011**, *17*, 777.
- [54] S.J. Bidarra, C.C. Barrias, M.A. Barbosa, R. Soares, P.L. Granja, *Biomacromolecules* **2010**, *11*, 1956.
- [55] M. Park, D. Lee, J. Hyun, *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2015**, *116*, 223.
- [56] L. Li, A.E. Davidovich, J.M. Schloss, U. Chippada, R.R. Schloss, N.A. Langrana, M.L. Yarmush, *Biomaterials* **2011**, *32*, 4489.
- [57] R. Yao, R. Zhang, F. Lin, J. Luan, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **2013**, *110*, 1430.
- [58] F. Cellesi, W. Weber, M. Fussenegger, J.A. Hubbell, N. Tirelli, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **2004**, *88*, 740.
- [59] Y. Dzenis, *Science* **2004**, *304*, 1917.
- [60] P. Rothmund, *Nature* **2006**, *440*, 297.
- [61] C.-H. Xue, J. Chen, W. Yin, S.-T. Jia, J.-Z. Ma, *App. Surf. Sci.* **2012**, *258*, 2468.
- [62] M.A. Daniele, D.A. Boyd, A.A. Adams, F.S. Ligler, *Adv. Healthcare Mater.* **2015**, *4*, 11.
- [63] T. Billiet, M. Vandenhaute, J. Schelfhout, S. van Vlierberghe, P. Dubruel, *Biomaterials* **2012**, *33*, 6020.
- [64] A. Kang, J. Park, J. Ju, G.S. Jeong, S.H. Lee, *Biomaterials* **2014**, *35*, 2651.
- [65] B.J. Vakoc, R.M. Lanning, J.A. Tyrrell, T.P. Padera, L.A. Bartlett, T. Stylianopoulos, L.L. Munn, G.J. Tearney, D. Fukumura, R.K. Jain, B.E. Bouma, *Nat. Med.* **2009**, *15*, 1219.
- [66] V.J. Wedeen, D.L. Rosene, R. Wang, G. Dai, F. Mortazavi, P. Hagmann, J.H. Kaas, W.-Y.I. Tseng, *Science* **2012**, *335*, 1628.
- [67] J. Cheng, Y. Jun, J. Qin, S.-H. Lee, *Biomaterials* **2017**, *114*, 121.

- [68] M. Hu, R. Deng, K.M. Schumacher, M. Kurisawa, H. Ye, K. Purnamawati, J.Y. Ying, *Biomaterials* **2010**, *31*, 863.
- [69] E. Kang, G. Jeong, Y. Choi, K. Lee, A. Khademhosseini, S. Lee, *Nat. Mater.* **2011**, *10*, 877.
- [70] K.H. Lee, S.J. Shin, Y. Park, S.-H. Lee, *Small* **2009**, *5*, 1264.
- [71] H. Onoe, T. Okitsu, A. Itou, M. Kato-Negishi, R. Gojo, D. Kiriya, K. Sato, S. Miura, S. Iwanaga, K. Kuribayashi-Shigetomi, Y.T. Matsunaga, Y. Shimoyama, S. Takeuchi, *Nat. Mater.* **2013**, *12*, 584.
- [72] N. Raof, M. Padgen, A. Gracias, M. Bergkvist, Y. Xie, *Biomaterials* **2011**, *32*, 4498.
- [73] S.-J. Shin, J.-Y. Park, J.-Y. Lee, H. Park, Y.-D. Park, K.-B. Lee, C.-M. Whang, S.-H. Lee, *Langmuir* **2007**, *23*, 9104.
- [74] S. Sugiura, T. Oda, Y. Aoyagi, M. Satake, N. Ohkohchic, M. Nakajimab, *Lab Chip* **2008**, *8*, 1255.
- [75] M. Yamada, S. Sugaya, Y. Naganuma, M. Seki, *Soft Matter* **2012**, *8*, 3122.
- [76] S. Zhang, M.A. Greenfield, A. Mata, L.C. Palmer, R. Bitton, J.R. Mantei, C. Aparicio, M.O. de la Cruz, S.I. Stupp, *Nat. Mater.* **2010**, *9*, 594.
- [77] D. Puppi, D. Dinucci, C. Bartoli, C. Mota, C. Migone, F. Dini, G. Barsotti, F. Carlucci, F. Chiellini, *J. Bioact. Compat. Polym.* **2011**, *26*, 478.
- [78] M. Hu, M. Kurisawa, R. Deng, C.M. Teo, A. Schumacher, Y.X. Thong, L. Wang, K.M. Schumacher, J.Y. Ying, *Biomaterials* **2009**, *30*, 3523.
- [79] B. Lee, K. Lee, E. Kang, D.-S. Kim, S.-H. Lee, *Biomicrofluidics* **2011**, *5*, 022208.
- [80] J.O. Buitrago, R.A. Perez, A. El-Fiqi, R.K. Singh, J.H. Kim, H.W. Kim, *Acta Biomater.* **2015**, *28*, 183.
- [81] F. Schwenter, B.L. Schneider, W.F. Pralong, N. Déglon, P. Aebischer, *Hum. Gene Ther.* **2004**, *15*, 669.
- [82] C.K. Colton, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2014**, *67*, 93.
- [83] J. Jansen, I.E. de Napoli, M. Fedecostante, C.M.S. Schophuizen, N.V. Chevtchik, L.P. Wilmer, M.J., van Asbeck, A.H., Croes, H.J., Pertijs, J.C., Wetzels, J.F.M., Hilbrands, L.B., van den Heuvel, J.G. Hoenderop, D. Stamatialis, R. Masereeuw, *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *5*, 16702.
- [84] M. Morada, S. Lee, L. Gunther-Cummins, L.M. Weiss, G. Widmer, S. Tzipori, N. Yarlett, *Int. J. Parasitol.* **2016**, *46*, 21.
- [85] S. Sakai, Y. Liu, E.J. Mah, M. Taya, *Biofabrication* **2013**, *5*, 015012.
- [86] T. Takei, N. Kishihara, S. Sakai, K. Kawakami, *Biochem. Eng. J.* **2010**, *49*, 143.
- [87] T. Yue, M. Nakajima, M. Takeuchi, C. Hu, Q. Huang, T. Fukuda, *Lab Chip* **2014**, *14*, 1151.
- [88] P. Sher, S.M. Oliveira, J. Borges, J.F. Mano, *Biofabrication* **2015**, *7*, 011001.
- [89] X. Shi, S. Ostrovidov, Y. Zhao, X. Liang, M. Kasuya, K. Kurihara, K. Nakajima, H. Bae, H. Wu, A. Khademhosseini, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2015**, *25*, 2250.
- [90] A. Leferink, D. Schipper, E. Arts, E. Vrij, N. Rivron, M. Karperien, K. Mittmann, C. van Blitterswijk, L. Moroni, R. Truckenmuller, *Adv. Mater.* **2014**, *26*, 2592.
- [91] P. Sher, C.R. Correia, R.R. Costa, J.F. Mano, *RSC Adv.* **2015**, *5*, 2511.
- [92] S. Ahadian, J. Ramón-Azcón, M. Estili, X. Liang, S. Ostrovidov, H. Shiku, M. Ramalingam, K. Nakajima, Y. Sakka, H. Bae, T. Matsue, A. Khademhosseini, *Sci. Rep.* **2014**, *4*, 1.
- [93] H. Qi, M. Ghodousi, Y. Du, C. Grun, H. Bae, P. Yin, A. Khademhosseini, *Nat. Commun.* **2013**, *4*, 1.
- [94] F. Xu, C.A. Wu, V. Rengarajan, T.D. Finley, H.O. Keles, Y. Sung, B. Li, U.A. Gurkan, U. Demirci, *Adv. Mater.* **2011**, *23*, 4254.
- [95] S. Guven, P. Chen, F. Inci, S. Tasoglu, B. Erkmén, U. Demirci, *Trends Biotechnol* **2015**, *33*, 269.
- [96] K. Yue, G.T.-de Santiago, M.M. Alvarez, A. Tamayol, N. Annabi, A. Khademhosseini, *Biomaterials* **2015**, *73*, 254.
- [97] H. Qi, Y. Du, L. Wang, H. Kaji, H. Bae, A. Khademhosseini, *Adv. Mater.* **2010**, *22*, 5276.
- [98] D.B. Kolesky, R.L. Truby, A.S. Gladman, T.A. Busbee, K.A., Homan, J.A., Lewis, *Adv. Mater.* **2014**, *26*, 3124.
- [99] J.S. Miller, K.R. Stevens, M.T. Yang, B.M. Baker, D.H. Nguyen, D.M. Cohen, E. Toro, A.A. Chen, P.A. Galie, X. Yu, R. Chaturvedi, S.N. Bhatia, C.S. Chen, *Nat. Mater.* **2012**, *11*, 768.
- [100] B. Duan, L.A. Hockaday, K.H. Kang, J.T. Butcher, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res., Part A* **2013**, *101A*, 1255.
- [101] L.A. Hockaday, K.H. Kang, N.W. Colangelo, P.Y.C. Cheung, B. Duan, E. Malone, J. Wu, L.N. Girardi, L.J. Bonassar, H. Lipson, *Biofabrication* **2012**, *4*, 035005.
- [102] S. Hong, D. Sycks, H.F. Chan, S. Lin, G.P. Lopez, F. Guilak, K.W. Leong, X. Zhao, *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *27*, 4035.

- [103] B. Zamanian, M. Masaeli, J.W. Nichol, M. Khabiry, M.J. Hancock, H. Bae, A. Khademhosseini, *Small* **2010**, *6*, 937.
- [104] A.P. McGuigan, D.A. Bruzewicz, A. Glavan, M.J. Butte, G.M. Whitesides, *PloS One* **2008**, *3*, e2258.
- [105] M.A. Stuart, W.T. Huck, J. Genzer, M. Muller, C. Ober, M. Stamm, G.B. Sukhorukov, I. Szleifer, V.V. Tsukruk, M., Urban, F. Winnik, S. Zauscher, I. Luzinov, S. Minko, *Nat. Mater.* **2010**, *9*, 101.
- [106] F. Meng, W. Hennink, Z. Zhong, *Biomaterials* **2009**, *30*, 2180.
- [107] N. Rapoport, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2007**, *32*, 962.
- [108] H.G. Schild, D.A. Tirrell, *J. Phys. Chem.* **1990**, *94*, 4352.
- [109] L. Klouda, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* **2015**, *97*, 338.
- [110] M. Patel, H.J. Lee, S. Park, Y. Kim, B. Jeong, *Biomaterials* **2018**, *159*, 91.
- [111] J.F. Mano, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* **2008**, *10*, 515.
- [112] T. Gan, Y. Guan, Y. Zhang, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2010**, *20*, 5937.
- [113] B.M. Watson, F.K. Kasper, P.S. Engel, A.G. Mikos, *Biomacromolecules* **2014**, *15*, 1788.
- [114] M. Lutolf, J. Lauer-Fields, H. Schmoekel, A. Metters, F. Weber, G. Fields, J. Hubbell, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2003**, *100*, 5413.
- [115] B.M. Watson, T.N. Vo, A.M. Tataru, S.R. Shah, D.W. Scott, P.S. Engel, A.G. Mikos, *Biomaterials* **2015**, *67*, 286.
- [116] B.L. Ekerdt, C.M. Fuentes, Y. Lei, M.M. Adil, A. Ramasubramanian, R.A. Segalman, D.V. Schaffer, *Adv. Healthcare Mater.* **2018**, *7*, 1800225.
- [117] J.M. Banks, L.C. Mozden, B.A.C. Harley, R.C. Bailey, *Biomaterials* **2014**, *35*, 8951.
- [118] W.J. Hadden, J.L. Young, A.W. Holle, M.L. Mcfetridge, D.Y. Kim, P. Wijesinghe, H. Taylor-Weiner, J.H. Wen, A.R. Lee, K. Bieback, B.-N. Vo, D.D. Sampson, B.F. Kennedy, J.P. Spatz, A.J. Engler, Y.S. Choi, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2017**, *114*, 5547.
- [119] A. Higuchi, Q.-D. Ling, Y. Chang, S.-T. Hsu, A. Umezawa, *Chem. Rev.* **2013**, *113*, 3297.
- [120] C.M. Madl, B.L. LeSavage, R.E. Dewi, C.B. Dinh, R.S. Stowers, M. Khariton, K.J. Lampe, D. Nguyen, O. Chaudhuri, A. Enejder, S.C. Heilshorn, *Nat. Mater.* **2017**, *16*, 1233.
- [121] J.H. Wen, L.G. Vincent, A. Fuhrmann, Y.S. Choi, K.C. Hribar, H. Taylor-Weiner, S. Chen, A.J. Engler, *Nat. Mater.* **2014**, *13*, 979.
- [122] M.Y. Hwang, S.G. Kim, H.S. Lee, S.J. Muller, *Soft Matter* **2017**, *13*, 5785.
- [123] X.M. Ma, R. Li, J. Ren, X.C. Lv, X.H. Zhao, Q. Ji, Y.Z. Xia, *RSC Advances* **2017**, *7*, 47767.
- [124] A.A. Thorpe, V. Boyes, C. Sammon, C. Le Maitre, *Acta Biomaterialia* **2016**, *36*, 99.
- [125] A.A. Thorpe, G. Dougill, L. Vickers, N.D. Reeves, C. Sammon, G. Cooper, C.L. Le Maitre, *Acta Biomaterialia* **2017**, *54*, 212.
- [126] A.R. Brunelle, C.B. Horner, K. Low, G. Ico, J. Nam, *Acta Biomater.* **2018**, *66*, 166.
- [127] H. Vihola, A. Laukkanen, L. Valtola, H. Tenhu, J. Hirvonen, *Biomaterials* **2005**, *26*, 3055.
- [128] R.L. Sala, M.Y. Kwon, M. Kim, S. Gullbrand, E.A. Henning, R.L. Mauck, E.R. Camargo, J.A. Burdick, *Tissue Eng., Part A* **2017**, *23*, 935.
- [129] D.W. Urry, M.M. Long, B.A. Cox, T. Ohnishi, L.W. Mitchell, M. Jacobs, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta, Protein Struct.* **1974**, *371*, 597.
- [130] A. Bandiera, *Exp. Opin. Drug Delivery* **2017**, *14*, 37.
- [131] C.M. Hwang, S. Sant, M. Masaeli, N.N. Kachouie, B. Zamanian, S.-H. Lee, A. Khademhosseini, *Biofabrication* **2010**, *2*, 035003.
- [132] W. Leong, T.T. Lau, D.A. Wang, *Acta Biomater.* **2013**, *9*, 6459.
- [133] H.H. Jung, K. Park, D.K. Han, *J. Controlled Release* **2010**, *147*, 84.
- [134] M.H. Cha, J. Choi, B.G. Choi, K. Park, I.-H. Kim, B. Jeong, D.K. Han, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2011**, *360*, 78.
- [135] J.H. Hong, H.J. Lee, B. Jeong, *ACS App. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, *9*, 11568.
- [136] R. Cruz-Acuña, M. Quirós, A.E. Farkas, P.H. Dedhia, S. Huang, D. Siuda, V. García-Hernández, A.J. Miller, J.R. Spence, A. Nusrat, A.J. García, *Nat. Cell Biol.* **2017**, *19*, 1336.
- [137] W.-H. Jian, H.-C. Wang, C.-H. Kuan, M.-H. Chen, H.-C. Wu, J.-S. Sun, T.-W. Wang, *Biomaterials* **2018**, *174*, 17.
- [138] W. Yan, W. Liu, J. Qi, Q. Fang, Z. Fan, G. Sun, Y. Han, D., Zhang, L. Xu, M. Wang, J. Li, F. Chen, D. Liu, R. Chai, H. Wang, *Mol. Neurobiol.* **2018**, *55*, 2070.
- [139] J. Zhang, L.-F. Chu, Z. Hou, M.P. Schwartz, T. Hacker, V. Vickerman, S. Swanson, N. Leng, B.K. Nguyen, A. Elwell, J. Bolin, M.E. Brown, R. Stewart, W.J. Burlingham, W.L. Murphy, J.A. Thomson, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **2017**, *114*, E6072.

- [140] D. Wang, A. Wang, F., Wu, X. Qiu, Y. Li, J. Chu, W.-C. Huang, K. Xu, X. Gong, S. Li, *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7*, 40295.
- [141] N. Kubota, N. Tatsumoto, T. Sano, K. Toya, *Carbohydr. Res.* **2000**, *324*, 268.
- [142] H. Tan, C.R. Chu, K.A. Payne, K.G. Marra, *Biomaterials* **2009**, *30*, 2499.
- [143] A. Chenite, C. Chaput, D. Wang, C. Combes, M.D. Buschmann, C.D. Hoemann, J.C. Leroux, B.L. Atkinson, F. Binette, A. Selmani, *Biomaterials* **2000**, *21*, 2155.
- [144] M. Lavertu, D. Fillion, M.D. Buschmann, *Biomacromolecules* **2008**, *9*, 640.
- [145] C.D.F. Moreira, S.M. Carvalho, H.S. Mansur, M.M. Pereira, *Mater. Sci. Eng., C* **2016**, *58*, 1207.
- [146] Q. Dang, K. Liu, Z. Zhang, C. Liu, X. Liu, Y. Xin, X. Cheng, T. Xu, D. Cha, B. Fan, *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2017**, *167*, 145.
- [147] K. Song, I. Li, X. Yan, W. Zhang, Y. Zhang, Y. Wang, T. Liu, *Mater. Sci. Eng., C* **2017**, *70*, 231.
- [148] N.-C. Cheng, W.-J. Lin, T.-Y. Ling, T.-H. Young, *Acta Biomater.* **2017**, *51*, 258.
- [149] A. Ressler, J. Ródenas-Rochina, M. Ivankovic, H. Ivankovic, A. Rogina, G.G. Ferrer, *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2018**, *197*, 469.
- [150] H. Naderi-Meshkin, K. Andreas, M.M. Matin, M. Sittinger, H.R. Bidkhori, N. Ahmadiankia, A.R. Bahrami, J. Ringe, *Cell Biol. Int.* **2014**, *38*, 72.
- [151] H. Sá-Lima, S.G. Caridade, J.F. Mano, R.L., *Soft Matter* **2010**, *6*, 5184.
- [152] C.V. Rahman, G. Kuhn, L.J. White, G.T. Kirby, O.P. Varghese, J.S. McLaren, H.C. Cox, F.R. Rose, R. Muller, J. Hilborn, K.M. Shakesheff, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res., Part B*, **2013**, *101*, 648.
- [153] P. de Vos, H.A. Lazarjani, D. Poncelet, M.M. Faas, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2014**, *67*, 15.
- [154] I. Mironi-Harpaz, D.Y. Wang, S. Venkatraman, D. Seliktar, *Acta Biomater.* **2012**, *8*, 1838.
- [155] B. Baroli, *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* **2006**, *81*, 491.
- [156] K.M. Gattas-Asfura, C.L. Stabler, *Biomacromolecules* **2009**, *10*, 3122.
- [157] B. Fairbanks, M. Schwartz, C. Bowman, K. Anseth, *Biomaterials* **2009**, *30*, 6702.
- [158] A.M.S. Costa, J.F. Mano, *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 15673.
- [159] A. Kloxin, A. Kasko, C. Salinas, K. Anseth, *Science* **2009**, *324*, 59.
- [160] A.M. Kloxin, M.W. Tibbitt, K.S. Anseth, *Nat. Protoc.* **2010**, *5*, 1867.
- [161] A.M. Kloxin, J.A. Bentona, K.S. Anseth, *Biomaterials* **2010**, *31*, 1.
- [162] A.M. Kloxin, M.W. Tibbitt, A.M. Kasko, J.A. Fairbairn, K.S. Anseth, *Adv. Mater.* **2010**, *22*, 61.
- [163] D.R. Griffin, A.M., Kasko, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 13103.
- [164] C.A. DeForest, K.S. Anseth, *Nat. Chem.* **2011**, *3*, 925.
- [165] C.A. DeForest, K.S. Anseth, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2012**, *124*, 1852.
- [166] M.W. Tibbitt, A.M. Kloxin, K.U. Dyamenahalli, K.S. Anseth, *Soft Matter* **2010**, *6*, 5100.
- [167] A.F. Demirörs, P.P. Pillai, B. Kowalczyk, B.A. Grzybowski, *Nature* **2013**, *503*, 99.
- [168] B.A. Grzybowski, H.A. Stone, G.M. Whitesides, *Nature* **2000**, *405*, 1033.
- [169] A. Snezhko, I. Aranson, *Nat. Mater.* **2011**, *10*, 698.
- [170] E. Castro, J.F. Mano, *J. Biomed. Nanotechnol.* **2013**, *9*, 1129.
- [171] Y. Li, G. Huang, X. Zhang, B. Li, Y. Chen, T. Lu, T.J. Lu, F. Xu, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2013**, *23*, 660.
- [172] J.M. Kanczler, H.S. Sura, J. Magnay, D. Green, R.O. Oreffo, J.P. Dobson, A.J. El Haj, *Tissue Eng., Part A* **2010**, *16*, 3241.
- [173] E. Popa, V. Santo, M. Rodrigues, M. Gomes, *Polymers* **2016**, *8*, 28.
- [174] J. Kim, D.R. Arifin, N. Muja, T. Kim, A.A. Gilad, H. Kim, A. Arepally, T. Hyeon, J.W. Bulte, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2011**, *50*, 2317.
- [175] L.B. Zhao, L. Pan, K. Zhang, S.S. Guo, W. Liu, Y. Wang, Y. Chen, X.Z. Zhao, H.L. Chan, *Lab Chip* **2009**, *9*, 2981.
- [176] R.G. Thomas, A.R. Unnithan, M.J. Moon, S.P. Surendran, T. Batgerel, C.H. Park, C.S. Kim, Y.Y. Jeong, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2018**, *110*, 465.
- [177] F. Xu, F. Inci, O. Mullick, U.A. Gurkan, Y. Sung, D. Kavaz, B. Li, E.B. Denkbaz, U. Demirci, *ACS Nano* **2012**, *6*, 6640.
- [178] Y. Wang, B. Li, Y. Zhou, D. Jia, *Polym. Ad. Technol.* **2008**, *19*, 1256.
- [179] H.-B. Xia, J. Yi, P.-S. Foo, B. Liu, *Chem. Mater.* **2007**, *19*, 4087.
- [180] S. Tasoglu, D. Kavaz, U.A. Gurkan, S. Guven, P. Chen, R. Zheng, U. Demirci, *Adv. Mater.* **2013**, *25*, 1137.
- [181] S. Tasoglu, C.H. Yu, H.I. Gungordu, S. Guven, T. Vural, U. Demirci, *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 4702.

- [182] C. Hu, M. Nakajima, H. Wang, T. Yue, Y. Shen, M. Takeuchi, Q. Huang, M. Seki, T. Fukuda, *IEE-NANO* **2013**, 14060453, 529.
- [183] T. Sun, Q. Huang, Q. Shi, H. Wang, X. Liu, M. Seki, M. Nakajima, T. Fukuda, *Microfluid. Nanofluid.* **2015**, 19, 1169.
- [184] E. Amis, *Nat. Mater.* **2004**, 3, 83.
- [185] P. Bianco, M. Riminucci, S. Gronthos, P. Robey, *Stem Cells* **2001**, 19, 180.
- [186] J.F. Mano, *Mater. Lett.* **2015**, 141, 198.
- [187] A.K. Jha, A. Mathur, F.L. Svedlund, J. Ye, Y. Yeghiazarians, K.E. Healy, *J. Controlled Release* **2015**, 209, 308.
- [188] R. Tsaryk, A. Gloria, T. Russo, L. Anspach, R. De Santis, S. Ghanaati, R.E. Unger, L. Ambrosio, C.J. Kirkpatrick, *Acta Biomater.* **2015**, 20, 10.
- [189] H.J. Lee, Y.H. Park, W.-G. Koh, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2013**, 23, 591.
- [190] O. Jeon, D.W. Wolfson, E. Alsberg, *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, 27, 2216.
- [191] J.N. Hunt, K.E. Feldman, N.A. Lynd, J. Deek, L.M. Campos, J.M. Spruell, B.M. Hernandez, E.J. Kramer, C.J. Hawker, *Adv. Mater.* **2011**, 23, 2327.
- [192] D.S. Benoit, M.P. Schwartz, A.R. Durney, K.S. Anseth, *Nat. Mater.* **2008**, 7, 816.
- [193] Y. Aizawa, R. Wylie, M. Shoichet, *Adv. Mater.* **2010**, 22, 4831.
- [194] R. Wylie, S. Ahsan, Y. Aizawa, K. Maxwell, C. Morshead, M. Shoichet, *Nat. Mater.* **2011**, 10, 799.
- [195] G. Orive, E. Santos, J.L. Pedraz, R.M. Hernandez, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2014**, 67-68, 3.
- [196] T. Hoshiba, H. Lu, N. Kawazoe, G. Chen, *Exp. Opin. Biol. Ther.* **2010**, 10, 1717.
- [197] E. Jabbari, J. Leijten, Q. Xu, A. Khademhosseini, *Mater. Today* **2016**, 19, 190.
- [198] C. Franz, K.M. Stewart, V.M. Weaver, *J. Cell Sci.* **2010**, 123, 4195.
- [199] F.M. Watt, W.T.S. Huck, *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol.* **2013**, 14, 467.
- [200] S.F. Badylak, D.O. Freytes, T.W. Gilbert, *Acta Biomater.* **2009**, 5, 1.
- [201] A. Shridhar, E. Gillies, B.G. Amsden, L.E. Flynn, in *Methods in Molecular Biology*, Springer Nature Switzerland **2017**, p. 1.
- [202] J. Visser, D. Gawlitta, K.E.M. Benders, S.M.H. Toma, B. Pouran, P.R. van Weeren, W.J.A. Dhert, J. Malda, *Biomaterials* **2015**, 37, 174.
- [203] G.N. Grover, N. Rao, K.L. Christman, *Nanotechnology* **2013**, 25, 014011.
- [204] E. Stocco, S. Barbon, D. Dalzoppo, S. Lora, L. Sartore, M. Folin, P.P. Parnigotto, C. Grandi, *BioMed Research International* **2014**, 2014, 762189.
- [205] P. Calvert, *Science* **2007**, 318, 208.
- [206] B. Guillotin, F. Guillemot, *Trends Biotechnol.* **2011**, 29, 183.
- [207] M. Marguet, C. Bonduelle, S. Lecommandoux, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, 42, 512.
- [208] S.-J. Song, J. Choi, Y.-D. Park, J.-J. Lee, S.Y. Hong, K. Sun, *Artif. Organs* **2010**, 34, 1044.
- [209] K. Sun, M. Liu, H. Liu, P. Zhang, J. Fan, J. Meng, S. Wang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2015**, 25, 4506.
- [210] A.M. Kushner, Z. Guan, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2011**, 50, 9026.
- [211] M. Antonietti, P. Fratzl, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, 211, 166.
- [212] N. Lewinski, V. Colvin, R. Drezek, *Small* **2008**, 4, 26.
- [213] Y.-C. Lu, W. Song, D. An, B.J. Kim, R. Schwartz, M. Wu, M. Ma, *J. Mater. Chem. B* **2015**, 3, 353.
- [214] S.M. Oliveira, R.L. Reis, J.F. Mano, *Biotechnol. Adv.* **2015**, 33, 842.